

Charles University, Faculty of Science
Univerzita Karlova, Přírodovědecká fakulta

Study programme: Botany
Studijní program: Botanika

UNIVERSITAS CAROLINA

Factors shaping microbial communities associated with ecologically
important bark beetles

Faktory ovlivňující složení mikrobiálních společenstev vázaných na
ekologicky významné kůrovce

Mgr. Karel Švec

Doctoral Thesis / *Disertační práce*

Supervisor / *Školitel*: doc. Mgr. Miroslav Kolařík, Ph.D.

Praha 2025

Declaration

Hereby, I declare that I have written the present Ph.D. thesis independently, using the listed references. The papers that form part of the thesis are co-authored, and author contributions are stated in the respective section. I have not used any part of this thesis to gain any other academic title.

Prohlášení

Prohlašuji, že jsem tuto disertační práci vypracovala nezávisle s použitím citované literatury. Publikace, které jsou součástí této práce mají spoluautory. Příspěvky jednotlivých autorů jsou uvedeny v příslušné sekci. Žádná část této práce nebyla použita pro získání jiného akademického titulu.

In Prague / V Praze 01. 06. 2025

Mgr. Karel Švec

„Die Natur ist ewig in neue und wunderbare Formen sich ergießend; wenn du ein offenes Auge hast, wirst du täglich neue Wunder sehen.“

"Nature is ever pouring forth new and marvelous forms; she is an exhaustless source of wonders, and if you have an eye for it, you will see them every day."

„Příroda je stále plná nekonečných zázraků; pokud máš oči, aby je viděly, a ducha, aby je pochopil.“

Johann Wolfgang von Goethe - Maxims and Reflections (posthumously published 1833)

„Die Wissenschaft kann das letzte Rätsel der Natur nicht lösen. Und das liegt daran, dass wir selbst Teil der Natur sind und daher Teil des Geheimnisses, das wir zu lösen versuchen.“

"Science cannot solve the ultimate mystery of nature. And that is because, in the last analysis, we ourselves are part of nature and therefore part of the mystery that we are trying to solve."

„Věda nemůže vyřešit ultimátní tajemství přírody. A to proto, že v poslední analýze jsme my sami součástí přírody, a proto i součástí tajemství, které se snažíme vyřešit.“

Max Planck - Where is Science Going? (1932)

Contents

Declaration	2
Prohlášení.....	2
List of original publications:	8
Publication 1 Proportions of taxa belonging to the gut core microbiome change throughout the life cycle and season of the bark beetle <i>Ips typographus</i>	8
Publication 2 New insight into the bark beetle <i>Ips typographus</i> bacteriome reveals unexplored diversity potentially beneficial to the host	8
Publication 3 Insight into the genomes of dominant yeast symbionts of European spruce bark beetle, <i>Ips typographus</i>	9
Manuscript 1 Metabolic synergy and complementarity in the <i>Ips typographus</i> holobiont ..	9
Manuscript 2 Organ specificity in taxonomically related ash bark beetles is accompanied by specific microbial communities	10
Poděkování.....	11
Acknowledgements	11
List of abbreviations:	12
Abstrakt	13
Klíčová slova:.....	13
Abstract	14
Keywords:.....	14
INTRODUCTION	14
Symbiosis as a fundamental ecological and evolutionary process	14
Using the term “Symbiosis”	16
Holobiont concept	16
Symbiosis in insects	17
Bark beetles as a model for studying insect–microbe symbioses	18
Mutual benefits of bark beetle-microbe symbiosis.....	21
Intestinal microbiome of bark beetles.....	22
Metabolic interactions in the bark beetle gut.....	22
Research aims and objectives	23
Main results	25

Proportions of taxa belonging to the gut core microbiome change throughout the life cycle and season of the bark beetle *Ips typographus*

Tereza Veselská^{1,†}, Karel Švec^{1,2,†}, Martin Kostovčík^{1,3}, Ezequiel Peral-Aranega^{4,5}, Paula Garcia-Fraile^{4,5}, Barbora Křížková¹, Václav Havlíček¹, Zaki Saati-Santamaría^{1,4,5}, Miroslav Kolařík^{1,†}

Publication 1 – Proportions of taxa belonging to the gut core microbiome change throughout the lifecycle and season of the bark beetle *I. typographus*25

Diversity and Composition of the Gut Microbiome in *I. typographus* Across Life Stages and Seasons.....25

Core Microbiome and Transmission Mechanisms27

Our analysis identified a core microbiome of *I. typographus* that persisted throughout the beetle’s life cycle and across the seasons. The fungal core microbiome included *Cyberlindnera* sp., *Kuraishia capsulata*, *K. molischiana*, *N. ambrosiae*, *O. neopini*, *O. ramenticola*, *Ophiostoma bicolor*, *Saccharomycopsis lassenensis*, *W. bisporus*, and *Yamadazyma scolyti*, while the bacterial core included *E. typographi*, *E. cedenensis*, *P. bohémica*, *Pseudoxanthomonas spadix*, *Rhizobium* sp., *Curtobacterium* sp., *Roseomonas* sp., *Serratia* sp., *Taibaiella* sp., and unidentified species of the family Sphingobacteriaceae, Lachnospiraceae, and Enterobacteriaceae.27

RESEARCH

Open Access

New insight into the bark beetle *ips typographus* bacteriome reveals unexplored diversity potentially beneficial to the host

Ezequiel Peral-Aranega^{1,2*}, Zaki Saati-Santamaría^{1,2,3}, Miguel Ayuso-Calles^{1,2}, Martin Kostovčík³, Tereza Veselská³, Karel Švec³, Raúl Rivas^{1,2,4}, Miroslav Kolařík³ and Paula García-Fraile^{1,2,3,4}

.....27

Publication 2 – New insight into the bark beetle *I. typographus* bacteriome reveals unexplored diversity potentially beneficial to the host27

Bacteriome Diversity and Taxonomic Composition27

Hydrolytic Enzyme Activity and Carbon Assimilation.....27

Antifungal Potential of the Bacteriome28

Core Bacteriome and Key Microbial Species.....28

Implications and Future Directions28

OPEN ACCESS

EDITED BY
 Yijuan Xu,
 South China Agricultural University, China

REVIEWED BY
 Ari Mikko Hietala,
 Norwegian Institute of Bioeconomy Research
 (NIBIO), Norway
 Eliane Ferreira Noronha,
 University of Brasilia, Brazil

Insight into the genomes of dominant yeast symbionts of European spruce bark beetle, *Ips typographus*

Tian Cheng^{1,2}, Tereza Veselská¹, Barbora Křížková¹, Karel Švec¹,
 Václav Havlíček¹, Marc Stadler² and Miroslav Kolařík^{1*}

.....29

Publication 3 – Insight into the genomes of dominant yeast symbionts of European spruce bark beetle, *Ips typographus*29

 Genome Sequencing and Analysis of Yeasts in the *I. typographus* Gut Microbiome29

 Carbohydrate-Active Enzymes (CAZymes) and Plant Cell Wall Degradation29

 Detoxification Mechanisms in Yeasts29

 Extracellular Enzyme Activities and Functional Implications30

 Symbiotic Roles in Nutrient Synthesis and Detoxification.....30

Preprints are preliminary reports that have not undergone peer review.
 They should not be considered conclusive, used to inform clinical practice,
 or referenced by the media as validated information.

Metabolic synergy and complementarity in the *Ips typographus* holobiont

Zaki Saati-Santamaría

zakisaati@usal.es

.....31

Manuscript 1 – Metabolic synergy and complementarity in the *Ips typographus* holobiont31

 Metatranscriptome Assembly and Taxonomic Composition31

 Functional Diversity and Holobiont Complementarity.....31

Despite the dominance of the beetle’s transcriptome in the dataset, bacteria and fungi contribute equally to the overall functional diversity within the holobiont. The PERMANOVA analysis revealed significant differences in life stages (p = 0.004), though the variability within groups was greater than between life stages, especially between larvae and adult beetles. This indicates that the microbial community plays a more pivotal role than life-stage-specific variations in shaping the functional outputs of the holobiont.31

 Microbial Contributions to Degradation of Plant and Fungal Cell Wall Polymers31

 Nitrogen Utilization within the Holobiont32

Nitrogen acquisition is critical for the beetle, given the nitrogen-limited environment in *Picea abies* phloem. Our results show that bacterial symbionts facilitate nitrogen acquisition, primarily through nitrate reduction to ammonia. The beetle’s microbiota also contributes to the conversion of uric acid into usable nitrogen sources, such as ammonia. Bacterial taxa like *Delftia*, *Erwinia*, and *Cupriavidus* are key players in this process. Fungi seem to rely on the ammonia produced by bacteria, scavenging it rather than contributing directly to ammonia conversion. This nitrogen cycle illustrates the essential role of microbial collaboration in overcoming the beetle’s nutritional constraints.32

Cross-Kingdom Cooperation in Amino Acid Metabolism32

Our analysis further revealed the intricate cooperation between beetle, bacteria, and fungi in amino acid metabolism. Essential amino acids such as histidine and lysine are synthesized by bacteria, with fungi playing a supporting role. However, the beetle largely depends on its symbiotic microbes for the synthesis of amino acids such as branched-chain amino acids (valine, leucine, isoleucine) and phenylalanine. This highlights the interdependence of the beetle and its microbial partners in synthesizing and interconverting amino acids. Notably, bacterial taxa such as *Erwinia*, *Delftia*, and *Phyllobacterium*, as well as fungal taxa like Sordariomycetes (including *Ophiostoma*), are key contributors to these pathways.32

Vitamin Co-Metabolism in the Holobiont.....32

Conclusion33

Organ specificity in taxonomically related ash bark beetles is accompanied by the specific microbial communities –

Křížková Barbora¹, Martin Kostovčík¹, Karel Švec¹, Oto Nakládál², Miroslav Kolařík^{1*}

.....33

Manuscript 2 - Organ specificity in taxonomically related ash bark beetles is accompanied by specific microbial communities33

Diversity and Taxonomic Composition.....33

Distinct fungal communities were linked to the beetle species:.....34

Community Structure and Differentiation.....34

Physiological Adaptations of Symbiotic Fungi34

Conclusion35

General discussion.....35

The specific requirements of life under the bark and the choice of a suitable model species35

Observed microbial diversity.....36

Identifying the core microbiome of *I. typographus*.....37

Acquisition and Localization of Gut Symbionts38

Metabolic complementarity within the *I. typographus* holobiont.....39

Gut microbiome benefits – direct study approaches40

Mycobiome benefits – Genomic study of <i>I. typographus</i> major fungal symbionts.....	43
Ecological filtering and symbiont divergence in 2 non-mycangial Ash bark beetles	45
Simplified Conclusions.....	46
Funding.....	47
References.....	47

List of original publications:

This thesis is based on the following five publications:

Publication 1 Proportions of taxa belonging to the gut core microbiome change throughout the life cycle and season of the bark beetle *Ips typographus*

Tereza Veselská & **Karel Švec***, Martin Kostovčík, Ezequiel Peral-Aranega, Paula Garcia-Fraile, Barbora Křížková, Václav Havlíček, Eñaki Saati-Santamaría, Miroslav Kolařík (2023). *FEMS Microbiology Ecology* 99 (8), fiad072

doi: 10.1093/femsec/fiad072

*Tereza Veselská & **Karel Švec** – shared first author position

Authors contribution: Tereza Veselská (Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Visualization, Writing – original draft), **Karel Švec** (Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Visualization, Writing – original draft), Martin Kostovčík (Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Software, Writing – original draft), Ezequiel Peral-Aranega (Formal analysis, Investigation), Paula Garcia-Fraile (Funding acquisition, Writing – review & editing), Barbora Křížková (Investigation), Václav Havlíček (Investigation), Eñaki Saati-Santamaría (Formal analysis, Investigation), and Miroslav Kolařík (Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Resources, Supervision, Validation, Writing – review & editing).

Publication 2 New insight into the bark beetle *Ips typographus* bacteriome reveals unexplored diversity potentially beneficial to the host

Ezequiel Peral-Aranega, Eñaki Saati-Santamaría, Miguel Ayuso-Calles, Martin Kostovčík, Tereza Veselská, **Karel Švec**, Raúl Rivas, Miroslav Kolařík, Paula García-Fraile. (2023). *Environmental Microbiome*

doi: 10.1186/s40793-023-00510-z

Authors contribution: Ezequiel Peral-Aranega (Investigation, Methodology, Software, Visualization, Writing – review & editing), Eñaki Saati-Santamaría (Formal analysis,

Investigation, Software, Writing – review & editing), Miguel Ayuso-Calles (Investigation), Martin Kostovčik (Investigation), Tereza Veselská (Investigation, Resources), **Karel Švec** (Investigation, Resources), Raúl Rivas (Resources, Supervision, Validation), Miroslav Kolařík (Conceptualization, Investigation, Project administration, Resources, Supervision, Validation), Paula García-Fraile (Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Funding acquisition, Methodology, Resources, Supervision, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft preparation).

Publication 3 Insight into the genomes of dominant yeast symbionts of European spruce bark beetle, *Ips typographus*

Tian Cheng, Tereza Veselská, Barbora Křížková, **Karel Švec**, Václav Havlíček, Marc Stadler, Miroslav Kolařík. (2023). *Frontiers in Microbiology*....

doi: 10.3389/fmicb.2023.1108975

Authors contribution: Tian Cheng (Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Software, Visualization, Writing – original draft), Tereza Veselská (Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing – review & editing), Barbora Křížková (Investigation), Karel Švec (Investigation, Resources, Writing – review & editing), Václav Havlíček (Investigation, Resources), Marc Stadler (Funding acquisition, Supervision), Miroslav Kolařík (Funding acquisition, Supervision, Validation).

Manuscript 1 Metabolic synergy and complementarity in the *Ips typographus* holobiont

Āaki Saati Santamaria & Karel Švec & Martin Kostovčik, Tereza Veselská, Miroslav Kolařík

Currently under review in ISME journal – 6/25

Preprint available on Research square; doi: 10.21203/rs.3.rs-5950784/v1

Authors contribution: Āaki Saati Santamaria (Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Software, Visualization, Writing – original draft), Karel Švec (Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Resources, Software, Visualization, Writing – review & editing), Martin Kostovčik (Investigation, Methodology, Software), Tereza Veselská (Investigation, Methodology, Writing – review & editing), Miroslav Kolařík (Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Supervision, Validation, Writing – review & editing).

Manuscript 2 Organ specificity in taxonomically related ash bark beetles is accompanied by specific microbial communities

Křížková Barbora, **Karel Švec**, Martin Kostovčík, Oto Nakládal, Miroslav Kolařík.

Authors contribution: Křížková Barbora (Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Visualization, Writing – original draft), Karel Švec (Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Resources, Software, Visualization, Writing – review & editing), Martin Kostovčík (Formal analysis, Software), Oto Nakládal (Resources), Miroslav Kolařík (Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Supervision, Validation, Writing – review & editing).

Poděkování

Rád bych poděkoval všem, kteří mě během mého předlouhého studia podporovali. Zvláštní poděkování patří mému školiteli Mirku Kolaříkovi, který mě přibral do svého týmu a vždy si našel čas na řešení čehokoliv co bylo zrovna třeba. Spíše, než za precizní systematické vedení mu děkuji za kreativní svobodu a možnost přicházet s vlastními nápady a projekty. Jsem mu velmi vděčný za vše, co jsem se od něj mohl naučit i když o tom on sám třeba ani netušil. Dále bych chtěl poděkovat paní Sylvě Pažoutové, Pavlu Špryňarovi a Jirkovi Gabrielovi, kteří mě provázeli mými prvními kroky ve světě vědy. Jirkovi Gabrielovi jest třeba přiznati obzvláštních zásluh. Za to, že se „mne ujal už jako středoškoláka“ a pomohl mi rozvinout můj zájem o pozoruhodný a vzrušující svět hub.

De děkuji celým kolektivům laboratoří Environmentální mikrobiologie („Baldrián lab“) a Genetiky a metabolismu hub („Kolařík lab“) Mikrobiologického ústavu Akademie věd ČR, ve které jsem pracoval na svém výzkumu. Naší laboratoře se patří vyzdvihnout zvláště Soňu Kajzrovou, Alenu Gabrielovou a Miladu Chudíčkovou nejen za poskytování životně důležitého technické zázemí pro laboratorní práci. De bych pak chtěl poděkovat mému studentstvu Vendulce Sedlákové za společně strávený čas v RNA boxu i mimo něj a Terezii Čihákové za možnost vyzkoušet si roli školitele.

V tomto poslední odstavci bych rád také poděkoval všem ostatním studentům a pedagogům katedry botaniky PŘF UK za konzultace, zejména Karlu Prášilovi, Ondřeji Koukolovi a Aleně Kubátové, kteří mě povzbuzovali a inspirovali k pokračování studia hub. Další zvláštní poděkování patří také všem mým spoluautorům a drahým kolegům z Braunschweigu, Jeny, Salamanky, Bangkoku, Gainsville, Njoro a Pretorie, bez nichž by tato práce nemohla vzniknout. Nakonec chci pak poděkovat své rodině a přátelům za jejich podporu a lásku, zejména pak mojí přítelkyni Mgr. Lence Machové z katedry Genetiky a mikrobiologie za péči, inspiraci a důvěru v momentech kdy jsem ji třeba já sám v sebe neměl. Úplně nakonec se pak omlouvám všem těm, na které jsem určitě zapomněl.

Acknowledgements

I would like to thank everyone who supported me throughout my lengthy studies. Special thanks go to my supervisor Mirek Kolařík, who welcomed me into his team and always found the time to address whatever issue arose. More than systematic and precise guidance, I thank him for the creative freedom and opportunity to pursue my ideas and projects. I am deeply grateful for

everything I learned from him, even when he might not have been aware of it himself. I also thank Sylva Pažoutová and Pavel Špryňar, who guided me through my initial steps in the scientific world. Special recognition belongs to Jirka Gabriel, who supported me as a high school student and nurtured my fascination with the remarkable and captivating world of fungi.

My thanks extend to the entire teams of the laboratories of Environmental Microbiology ("Baldrian lab") and Genetics and Metabolism of Fungi ("Kolařík lab") at the Institute of Microbiology, Czech Academy of Sciences, where I conducted my research. Within our lab, particular gratitude goes to Soňa Kajzrová, Alena Gabrielova and Milada Chudíčková, who provided essential technical support for my laboratory work. Additionally, I would like to thank my students, Vendulka Sedláková and Terezie Čiháková, for the enjoyable times we spent both in and outside the RNA box, and for allowing me to experience the role of a supervisor.

In this final paragraph, I would like to express my appreciation to all students and teachers from the Department of Botany, Faculty of Science at Charles University, especially Karel Prášil, Ondřej Koukol, and Alena Kubátová, whose consultations encouraged and inspired me to continue studying fungi. Further special thanks are owed to all my co-authors and esteemed colleagues from Braunschweig, Jena, Salamanca, Bangkok, Gainesville, Njoro, and Pretoria, without whom this work would not have been possible. Finally, I wish to thank my family and friends for their support and love, particularly my girlfriend, Mgr. Lenka Machová (Department of Genetics and Microbiology, UK), for her care, inspiration, and trust in moments when I myself lacked confidence. Lastly, I apologize to anyone whom I may have unintentionally overlooked.

List of abbreviations:

LMO – large multicellular organisms

ASV – amplicon sequence variants

ANCOM – Analysis of Composition of Microbiomes

ORFs – open reading frames

KEGG – Kyoto Encyclopedia of Genes and Genomes

GO - gene ontology

CA₂y – carbohydrate-active enzymes

GH – glycoside hydrolase

CE – carbohydrate esterases

PL – polysaccharide lyases

ATP – Adenosine triphosphate

ABC – ATP-binding cassette

eDNA – environmental deoxyribonucleic acid

eRNA – environmental ribonucleic acid

TEM – Transmission electron microscope

ITS – Internal transcribed spacer

TEF1 α – Translation elongation factor 1-alpha

CMC – carboxymethyl cellulose

CYPs – Cytochrome P450

Abstrakt

Mikrobiální symbionti kůrovců (bakterie a houby) významně ovlivňují jejich ekologii, vývoj a schopnost přežít v extrémně nehostinném prostředí floému hostitelských stromů. Tato práce se zaměřuje na identifikaci faktorů, které formují složení a funkci mikrobiálních společenstev spojených s třemi významnými evropskými druhy kůrovců – zejména lýkožroutem smrkovým (*Ips typographus*) a dvěma zástupci rodu *Hylesinus*. Za využití kombinace kultivačních, amplikonových, genomických, transkriptomických a mikroskopických postupů byly testovány hypotézy, zda (i) složení střevního mikrobiomu je určováno vývojovým stadiem brouka, sezónou a mikrohabitatem, (ii) jednotliví mikrobiální symbionti plní specifické metabolické funkce v rámci holobiontu a (iii) dochází k vertikálnímu přenosu symbiontů mezi generacemi. Výsledky ukazují, že druhové složení střevního „core mikrobiomu“ je stabilní v čase a napříč vývojovými stádii. Bakterie a houby v prostředí střeva *I. typographus* vykazují metabolickou komplementaritu – podílí se na rozkladu lignocelulózy, syntéze vitamínů a aminokyselin, a zejména na recyklaci dusíku. Významná proporce izolovaných bakterií vykazovala schopnost potlačit růst entomopatogenních hub v prostředí *in vitro*. Nepotvrdili jsme hypotézu o biologické fixaci dusíku v mikrohabitatu *I. typographus*; místo toho ve studovaném prostředí bakterie transformuje dusičnany a kyselinu močovou na amoniak, který je pak společenstvem dále využitelný. Práce přináší nový funkční pohled na ekologii některých kůrovců a objasňuje mechanismy, kterými mikrobiální symbióza podporuje jejich adaptaci na nehostinné prostředí lýka stromů.

Klíčová slova:

Kůrovci, floém, symbióza, mikrobiom, mutualismus, houby, bakterie, kvasinky, patogeny

Abstract

Microbial symbionts of bark beetles, including both bacteria and fungi, play a crucial role in their ecology, development, and survival within the extremely nutrient-poor and hostile environment of host tree phloem. This dissertation focuses on identifying the factors that shape the composition and function of microbial communities associated with three ecologically important European bark beetles—particularly the spruce bark beetle (*Ips typographus*) and two species of the genus *Hylesinus*. By integrating cultivation-based methods, amplicon sequencing, genomics, metatranscriptomics, and microscopy, the study tested the hypotheses that (i) gut microbiome composition is structured by the beetle's developmental stage, season, and microhabitat, (ii) individual microbial symbionts perform specific metabolic functions within the holobiont, and (iii) symbionts are vertically transmitted across generations. The results show that the species composition of the *core gut microbiome* remains temporally stable and consistent across life stages. In *I. typographus*, bacterial and fungal symbionts display marked metabolic complementarity, contributing to lignocellulose degradation, vitamin and amino acid biosynthesis, and especially nitrogen recycling. A substantial proportion of isolated bacterial strains exhibited antifungal activity against entomopathogenic fungi *in vitro*. The hypothesis of atmospheric nitrogen fixation was not supported; instead, symbionts transform nitrate and uric acid into ammonia, which serves as a communal nitrogen source. This thesis provides novel insights into the functional ecology of bark beetles and clarifies how microbial symbioses support their adaptation to the challenging environment of tree phloem.

Keywords:

Bark beetles, phloem, symbiosis, microbiome, mutualism, fungi, bacteria, yeasts, pathogens, transcriptome, genome

INTRODUCTION

Symbiosis as a fundamental ecological and evolutionary process

Symbiosis is an often discreet but widespread interaction with fundamental importance for most terrestrial, freshwater, and marine ecosystems (Cavanaugh et al., 2013; Hammer et al., 2019; Mondal et al., 2023; Moran, 2006, 2007). Although the importance of symbiosis as a factor driving evolutionary mechanisms was overlooked in the early days of modern organismal science, there has been a paradigm shift in recent decades towards emphasizing the importance of cooperation

between organisms. Importance can be demonstrated by the genesis of organelles, such as plastids and mitochondria, in eukaryotic cells, which dramatically increased the complexity and abilities of cells and ultimately allowed life in the form of plants to leave the sea and colonize the terrestrial environment extensively. Similarly, symbiosis with microorganisms had a major impact on animals, allowing them to develop new ecological niches by accessing otherwise unavailable food sources (Gibson & Hunter, 2010; Moran, 2006; Moran et al., 2005). However, it is necessary to study the cases of interactions carefully, to observe individual cases and to avoid overgeneralizations (Hammer et al., 2019; Moran & Yun, 2015).

The mechanisms involved in establishing and sustaining symbiotic relationships differ, encompassing variations in the microbe's role in host biology, the evolutionary background of the association, and the genomic characteristics of the microorganism. Certain symbiotic interactions exhibit high specialization and stability, seemingly limiting the potential for evolutionary innovations in host lineages. Conversely, some are characterized by dynamism, where symbiont genomes serve as gateways for introducing novel genes that impact host ecology (Moran, 2006).

Microorganisms were the first forms of complex life; they formed about 3.5 billion years ago (prokaryotes, ~3,5My (Allwood et al., 2007) and fungi ~1,5My (Wang et al., 1999)), and therefore, they diversified earlier than large multicellular organisms (LMO). Later evolving LMO provided microorganisms with a new, persistent and rich sources and stable niches (Moran, 2006; Schopf et al., 2018). One of the important aspects of symbiosis is its genesis and continuity, which are closely related to its modes of transmission. These connections are often permanent for the hosts and are often transmitted vertically across generations. Lifestyles of organisms involved in symbiosis may already be so fused that they cannot exist without cooperation. Their mutual bond is so strong that they cannot be recognized as separate entities at first sight (Moran, 2006). Lichens are one of the best examples of this phenomenon. The recent acceleration of knowledge in this field is directly related to introducing new methodological approaches such as molecular biology methods (Mondal et al., 2023; Moran, 2006).

Another aspect to mention is coevolution and the associated codiversification of organisms in the symbiotic state. Complex interactions between insects and their microbial symbionts are an ideal model for studying this phenomenon. Utilizing genomic methods has significantly advanced our comprehension of metabolism within natural microbial communities overall, with a specific focus on symbiotic systems (Gibson & Hunter, 2010).

Mutualism might be obligatory for the host, the symbiont, both, or none. The extensively examined instances revolve typically around extremely specialized partnerships, wherein both entities can exist solely in each other's presence (Moran, 2006). Differences in the tightness of coexistence between the host and symbiont lead to differences in genome evolution of the symbiont as well as of the host (Moran, 2006). In the evolutionary process, some of these tightly associated organisms experienced the loss of genes responsible for encoding enzymes essential in the biosynthesis of numerous vital organic compounds (e.g. riboflavin pathway in Aphids (Monnin et al., 2020)). Consequently, animals dependent on symbionts face limitations in their capacity to produce various compounds necessary for cellular function and exhibit restrictions in utilizing diverse energy sources (Moran, 2006).

Using the term “Symbiosis”

In this dissertation thesis and our attached publications, the term “symbiosis” is used primarily to refer to mutualistic interactions between bark beetles (Curculionidae: Scolytinae) and their microbial partners (bacteria and fungi). Although in ecological literature, the concept of symbiosis broadly encompasses all types of close interspecific interactions, including parasitism, commensalism, and predation (Boucher, 2016; Douglas, 2021; Thorpe, 1953), in this work it is applied specifically to interactions that provide functional benefits to both partners, i.e., mutualisms. This focus reflects the common usage in insect–microbe research, where the term “symbiont” typically refers to microbial partners involved in nutrient provision, detoxification, or defense (Biedermann & Vega, 2020; Moran, 2006), all of which contribute to the ecological success of the host.

Holobiont concept

In recent years, the concept of the “holobiont” has become an important ecological and evolutionary framework for understanding the relationships between multicellular organisms and their associated microbiota (Gilbert et al., 2012; Mindell, 1992). In this dissertation, the bark beetle holobiont is understood as the integrated unit formed by the insect host together with its symbiotic microorganisms, including bacteria, yeasts, and filamentous fungi (Six, 2013). This concept emphasizes the close metabolic and ecological interdependence between the beetle and its microbial partners, which enables the colonization of nutritionally challenging habitats (Moran, 2007), and the exploitation of otherwise inaccessible resources (Klepzig & Six, 2004). The holobiont perspective also highlights the role of microbes in modulation of the host physiology, including detoxification, immune interactions, and ecological adaptation (Biedermann & Vega, 2020; Moran, 2007). In non-mycangial bark beetles, the holobiont is shaped

by a combination of vertical as well as horizontal transmission routes, which influences the stability and flexibility of these associations across environmental gradients and life stages (Biedermann & Vega, 2020; Moran, 2007).

Symbiosis in insects

Microbial symbiosis is widespread among insects and plays a fundamental role in insect behavior and life strategies (Biedermann & Vega, 2020; Hosokawa & Fukatsu, 2020; Lu et al., 2016; Vidal et al., 2021). Insects are often strict dietary specialists, shaped by a long-term coevolution with microbes, which has driven the development of specialized phoretic strategies and organs, including the formation of mycangia (specialized organs adapted for transport of symbiotic fungi) (Calevro et al., 2023). Obligate symbiosis between insects and microbes is an attractive and well-studied topic, e.g., in *Atta* leaf-cutter ants and termites (Schultz & Brady, 2008). Ambrosia beetles are representatives of obligate symbiosis within bark beetles, where mycangia play a crucial role (Skelton et al., 2019). This group of bark beetles is not studied in our work and will therefore be mentioned here only marginally, despite being considered an example of one of the most successful symbiotic relationships among bark beetles and their fungal symbionts (Skelton et al., 2019).

The less stringent type of association is facultative symbiosis, which is not strictly required for host survival, and its typical attributes are conditional beneficence, horizontal transmission, and dynamic interactions compared to obligate symbiosis (Klepzig & Six, 2004; Moran, 2006; Six & Klepzig, 2021).

feature	Obligatory Symbionts	Non-Obligatory Symbionts
Dependency	a host cannot survive without	Host survives
Transmission	strictly vertical	Vertical + horizontal
Genome	reduced	Less reduced

Functional Role	core metabolism (e.g. nutrition)	Defense, stress tolerance, communication
------------------------	----------------------------------	--

It has been reported that nutritional benefits to hosts are commonly promoted by long-term coevolution and genome stasis of microbial symbionts (Moran, 2006). This phenomenon has been described in the aphid–*Buchnera* system, where, over evolutionary time, bacteria have undergone significant genome reduction, stabilizing in a state that specifically supports the nutritional needs of the host ((Mondal et al., 2023; Moran, 2006, 2007; Moran & Telang, 1998; Moran & Yun, 2015; Ummah et al., 2020)) see table 1.

Tab 1. Feature comparison based on: (Baumann, 2005; Chen et al., 2017; Ferrari & Vavre, 2011; Mondal et al., 2023; Moran, 2006; Moran & Telang, 1998; Moran & Yun, 2015)

The mechanism by which microbial symbionts are carried is a key feature important for understanding their mode of action. Various food specialists, such as ambrosia beetles, have developed (thanks to long coevolution – Mayers 2020) specific organs called “mycangia” for the sophisticated retention and phoresy of their vital microbial symbionts (Skelton et al., 2019). These specific organs are also found in some aggressive bark beetles (Six et al., 2011; Six & Wingfield, 2011).

Other bark beetles, including *I. typographus* or *Hylesinus* species, studied in the following publications, rely on less specific means for symbiont transmission. These non-mycangial bark beetles are commonly associated with Ophiostomatoid fungi or fungi from the genus *Geosmithia* (B. J. Bentz et al., 2019; Biedermann et al., 2019a; B. R. Jankowiak, 2005). These ectosymbionts are passively carried on the cuticle surface (in tiny pits or hairs). Adaptation of filamentous fungi for this trait involves the massive production of sticky and highly adhesive conidia and ascospores or yeast growth within a viscous extracellular matrix (e.g. Saccharomycetales). These adaptations help them adhere to the beetles’ cuticle. This significantly enhances the probability of fungi being transferred by the bark beetle to the new habitat (B. J. Bentz et al., 2019; Biedermann et al., 2019a; Hammerbacher et al., 2013; Six & Wingfield, 2011). Alternatively, symbiotic microbes can be carried in the gut lumen. These gut symbionts are typically represented by bacteria and yeast (Saccharomycetales)(Baños-Quintana et al., 2024).

Bark beetles as a model for studying insect–microbe symbioses

Bark beetles represent a highly diverse and ecologically significant group of insects, with approximately 6000 described species worldwide (Kirkendall et al., 2015; Wood & Bright, 1992). Their life strategies range from primary bark beetles, capable of killing healthy trees, to secondary

species colonizing weakened or dead trees, and saprophytic species that exploit decaying plant tissue (Kirkendall et al., 2015; Paine et al., 1997). Bark beetles play a crucial role in shaping of forest ecosystems, serving as major disturbance agents and contributing to forest dynamics, nutrient cycling, and biodiversity (Seidl et al., 2017; Six, 2020).

Bark beetles themselves are an important agent of disturbance of forest ecosystems, and their massive outbreaks often occur in forest ecosystems weakened by unfavorable weather conditions, such as ongoing drought or, conversely, storms accompanied by winds, or (in the case of production forests) by inappropriate management (B. Bentz et al., 2009; Davis et al., 2020; Hlásny et al., 2019, 2021a; Kulakowski, 2016; Lundquist, 2019; Rodman et al., 2021). This makes the topic of bark beetle outbreaks an intensely studied and important issue from a human socio-economic perspective. This situation is compounded by global climate change, which, in conjunction with inappropriate management, creates a positive feedback loop that worsens the situation (Baños-Quintana et al., 2024; Biedermann et al., 2019a; Hlásny et al., 2019; Jaime et al., 2023) (see Fig. 1.), not only in Europe but also in North America (B. Bentz et al., 2009; Fettig et al., 2022; Six, 2020) and Asia (Karpov et al., 2024).

Bark beetles are recognized as key drivers of ecosystem structure and function in temperate and boreal forests. They contribute to forest heterogeneity and biodiversity by causing tree diebacks, which create opportunities for the growth of understory plants (Kulakowski, 2016) and consequently promote the presence of pollinators (Davis et al., 2020). On the other hand, they can cause extensive tree mortality during the mentioned outbreaks, which impacts carbon storage, nutrient cycling, and water resource provisioning. The fundamental impact of bark beetles on ecosystems has been described as a “knock-on effect,” referring to their ability to trigger chain reactions within the forest systems (Biedermann et al., 2019a; Jaime et al., 2023; Six & Wingfield, 2011). Some authors point to the increased risk associated with environmental change and bark beetle outbreaks, especially in silvicultural monocultural forests (see Fig. 1). The risk of destructive outbreaks can be supported by common inadequate forest management, as well as the introduction of new, potentially invasive species through international trade (B. J. Bentz et al., 2010; Biedermann et al., 2019b; Hlásny et al., 2021a; Mezei et al., 2017).

Fig. 1. (Biedermann et al., 2019a) Precise “map” of the complex relationships and dynamics between the bark beetles, host (tree host) and their associated microbes, predators, parasites and the environment itself. Original description in Biedermann 2019: “(I) Major climatic variables affected by climate change at a macro- and regional scale. (II) The most important variables relating to the properties of individual host trees and trees at a landscape scale. (III) Main population phases (non-outbreak, build-up, outbreak, collapse) of an eruptive insect species. (IV) Major biotic variables associated with an eruptive insect species, plus intraspecific effects (phenotype, genotype, and intraspecific competition). Arrows are exemplary of the *Ips typographus* system. An arrow from one of the boxes in group I, II, or IV to one of the boxes in group III would indicate a direct effect on the population phases

of the beetle. Arrows connecting multiple boxes and eventually pointing to one of the four population phases would indicate an indirect effect. The grey arrows represent hypotheses that have yet to be tested and thus mirror gaps in our knowledge of the *I. typographus*. The absence of an arrow between boxes implies that there is probably no effect of one variable on another in the *I. typographus*”.

Mutual benefits of bark beetle-microbe symbiosis

One of the most fascinating aspects of bark beetle biology is their cooperation with various microbial partners, including filamentous fungi, yeasts, and bacteria (Hofstetter et al., 2015; Hosokawa & Fukatsu, 2020; Mondal et al., 2023; Moran, 2006; Six & Wingfield, 2011). These symbionts perform various functions, such as facilitating nutrient acquisition, degrading host plant defences, providing detoxification capabilities, and mediating aggregation and host recognition (Boone et al., 2013; Hulcr & Stelinski, 2017; Shamjana et al., 2024). Fungal associates, particularly species of *Ophiostoma*, *Ceratocystiopsis*, *Grosmannia*, or *Geosmithia*, play an essential role in the nutritional ecology of bark beetles and contribute to the success of tree colonization (Kirisits, 2004; Kolařík & Hulcr, 2023; Paine et al., 1997; Zhao et al., 2019).

The transmission of symbionts in bark beetles is highly variable. It includes both specialized structures, such as mycangia, which ensure vertical transmission of fungal partners, and horizontal acquisition of microbes from galleries or the surrounding environment (Hulcr & Stelinski, 2017; Klepzig & Six, 2004). Interestingly, some bark beetles without mycangia still maintain consistent associations with yeasts or fungi, highlighting the flexibility and evolutionary importance of these partnerships (Lehenberger et al., 2021).

Bark beetles have therefore emerged as an important model system for studying insect-microbe symbioses, providing insights into the ecological, functional, and evolutionary dynamics of complex multipartite interactions. Their ecological relevance, wide range of symbiotic strategies, and increasing availability of genomic resources make them an exceptional system for understanding the role of microbes in insect adaptation and diversification.

In this dissertation, three bark beetle species (*I. typographus*, *H. crenatus* and *H. fraxini*) were selected to study various aspects of symbiosis between ecologically important European bark beetles and their microbial symbionts. *I. typographus* was chosen as a model species, as its genome (Powell et al., 2021) and transcriptomes (Andersson et al., 2013; Ramakrishnan et al., 2022) are already available. Its associated microbial communities have been extensively studied through traditional cultivation-based methods over several decades (Fabryová et al., 2018; García-Fraile, 2018; R. Jankowiak, 2005; R. Jankowiak & Hilszczański, 2005; Linnakoski

et al., 2012). Moreover, its impact on the environment, economics and human populations is immense (Biedermann et al., 2019b). In contrast, both *Hylesinus crenatus* and *H. fraxini*, although belonging to the same genus, were selected to represent contrasting symbiotic strategies. *Hylesinus crenatus* is known to be associated with ophiostomatoid fungi and attacks ash (*Fraxinus sp.*) tree trunks, whereas *H. fraxini* is strictly associated with the *Geosmithia* genus and colonizes smaller ash branches (Strzátka et al., 2021). This combination of species enables a comparative analysis across different symbiotic associations, host tree species, and ecological strategies, providing a robust framework for investigating the ecological and evolutionary roles of microbial symbionts in bark beetles (Kirschner, 2001).

Intestinal microbiome of bark beetles

The intestinal microbiome of bark beetles represents a diverse and dynamic community of microorganisms, including bacteria, yeasts, and filamentous fungi. Bacterial genera frequently documented in the guts of bark beetles include *Enterobacter* and *Rahnella* (Morales-Jiménez et al., 2012a), *Pseudomonas* (Adams et al., 2013a; Fabryová et al., 2018), *Serratia* and *Stenotrophomonas* (Fabryová et al., 2018; Saati-Santamaría et al., 2021). The yeast microbiome is often represented by species of *Candida*, *Cyberlindnera*, *Ogataea* and *Wickerhamomyces* (Boone et al., 2013). These communities of gut-microbiome are shaped by both environmental acquisition and vertical transmission (Bracewell & Six, 2015; Six, 2013; Six & Biedermann, 2023; Zhou et al., 2016), with specific taxa consistently reported across different bark beetle species and life stages (Adams et al., 2013a). The composition of the gut microbiome is influenced by host tree species (Morales-Jiménez et al., 2012a), developmental stage (Boone et al., 2013), and ecological conditions (Zhou et al., 2016), reflecting the complex interactions between beetles, their diet, and their microbial partners.

Metabolic interactions in the bark beetle gut

Microbial symbionts in the gut of bark beetles perform a variety of metabolic functions that support host survival in nutritionally challenging environments. These include the degradation of recalcitrant plant polymers such as cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin (Adams et al., 2013a), as well as the hydrolysis of chitin derived from fungal and insect material (Boone et al., 2013). Symbionts contribute to nitrogen cycling through processes such as nitrogen fixation and ammonium assimilation (Morales-Jiménez et al., 2012a), and they play roles in the recycling of nitrogenous waste products such as uric acid (Zhou et al., 2016), thereby providing essential amino acids to the host (Morales-Jiménez et al., 2012a). Additionally, microbial communities

in the beetle gut are involved in the biosynthesis of B vitamins, sterols, and fatty acids (Boone et al., 2013), which are crucial for development and reproduction. Some bacteria and yeasts also participate in the detoxification of plant secondary metabolites, including terpenoids and phenolic compounds (Adams et al., 2013a), reducing the chemical defenses of host trees and facilitating beetle colonization (Zhou et al., 2016). Importantly, recent research has shown that gut bacteria regulate glucose transport in bark beetle larvae by inducing gut hypoxia and secreting riboflavin, which activates host hypoxia-inducible factors to upregulate glucose transporters, thereby promoting nutrient absorption and larval development (Liu et al. 2024).

Research aims and objectives

The main objective of this dissertation is to increase our current understanding of the functioning of mutualistic relationships between bark beetles and their associated microorganisms, integrating ecological, genomic, and functional perspectives. This work represents an almost decade-long effort to elucidate the dynamics, evolution, and complexity of this symbiotic multitrophic system, approached primarily from the standpoint of environmental ecology rather than pest management.

Specifically, three bark beetle species were selected to explore various aspects of symbiosis between ecologically important European bark beetles and their microbial symbionts. *I. typographus* was chosen as a “well-known” model species due to the availability of genomic and transcriptomic resources and because its associated microbial communities have been extensively studied using cultivation-based approaches. In contrast, *H. crenatus* and *H. fraxini* were selected to represent two closely related species with contrasting symbiotic strategies, thereby broadening our understanding of symbiosis in less-explored non-model systems.

While initial research has highlighted the importance of microbial symbionts in bark beetles, key aspects such as defining the core microbiome and understanding its succession across the life cycle have remained largely unaddressed, leaving several critical knowledge gaps. A general understanding is lacking explanation of how the multitrophic environment of the bark beetle gut functions, what specific roles bacteria and fungi play, and how microbial community composition changes across the host life cycle and influences gut-associated processes. More broadly, there is limited knowledge of the evolutionary adaptations that enable microbial symbionts to function as mutualists in the bark beetle gut environment. These gaps are particularly relevant in the case of *I. typographus*, where dominant yeast and bacterial symbionts have been described, but their functional and ecological roles remain poorly understood. In *H. crenatus* and *H. fraxini*, the ecological drivers shaping microbial communities are largely unknown, and it remains to be

verified what specific features drive the associations of bark beetles either with genus *Geosmithia* or ophiostomatoid fungi (an ecological, paraphyletic group of several ascomycetous genera from orders Ophiostomatales, Microascales, Hypocreales and Saccharomycetales). This dissertation resolves the addressed knowledge gaps by combining “traditional” cultivation-dependent and cultivation-independent (DNA/RNA metabarcoding) approaches, genomic and functional analyses, combined with physiological experiments and various types of microscopy.

The main aims of this dissertation are to:

- Describe the composition of microbiomes in 3 important bark beetle species.
 - Define the core gut microbiome of *I. typographus* and describe its seasonal and ontogenetic dynamics.
 - Characterize the microbial communities associated with ash bark beetles, *H. fraxini* and *H. crenatus*.
- Evaluate the metabolic activities and functional ecological roles of dominant fungal and bacterial symbionts in *I. typographus* gut microbiome.
- Present a taxonomic microbial analysis of *I. typographus* across different life stages using culture-dependent and -independent techniques.
- Study potential ecological roles of the *I. typographus* microbiome, identifying key taxa involved in nutrient acquisition and pathogen defense.
- Sequence and analyze genomes of major symbiotic yeasts associated with *I. typographus*.
- Investigate environmental factors driving microbiome specialization within *Hylesinus* bark beetle species.
- Evaluate trophic interactions within the gut ecosystems of bark beetles.
- Determine the metabolic roles of bacteria and fungi in the gut of *I. typographus* and related species.

Main results

This dissertation brings together 3 publications in IF journals and 2 submitted manuscripts. All of them focus on microbial communities (fungi and bacteria) associated with their hosts - bark beetles affecting European forest ecosystems. Publications 1-3 and Manuscript 1 study the European spruce bark beetle *I. typographus*, the succession process of its gut microbiome and selected features of dominant microbes present in the mentioned system. Manuscript 2 focuses on the question of preference of dominant fungal symbiont (*Geosmithia* associated type versus Ophiostomatoid fungi associated type) in 2 closely related species of single genus (*Hylesinus fraxini* versus *H. crenatus*), evaluating the composition of their associated communities and physiological features of symbiotic fungi (*Ophisotoma* and *Geosmithia* species) to explain this rigid association scheme of “symbiont preference”. In the following paragraphs, I will present and comment on selected results from each article.

FEMS Microbiology Ecology, 2023, 99, 1–15

DOI: 10.1093/femsec/fiad072

Advance access publication date: 27 June 2023

Research Article

Proportions of taxa belonging to the gut core microbiome change throughout the life cycle and season of the bark beetle *Ips typographus*

Tereza Veselská^{1,†}, Karel Švec^{1,2,†}, Martin Kostovčík^{1,3}, Ezequiel Peral-Aranega^{4,5}, Paula Garcia-Fraile^{1,4,5}, Barbora Křížková¹, Václav Havlíček¹, Zaki Saati-Santamaría^{1,4,5}, Miroslav Kolařík^{1,*}

Publication 1 – Proportions of taxa belonging to the gut core microbiome change throughout the lifecycle and season of the bark beetle *I. typographus*

Diversity and Composition of the Gut Microbiome in *I. typographus* Across Life Stages and Seasons

We used molecular methods, including eDNA and eRNA metabarcoding as well as traditional cultivation techniques, to examine the active gut microbiomes of *I. typographus*. This dual approach allowed us to capture a comprehensive view of the microbial community across the beetle's entire life cycle, from parental adults to larvae, pupae, and teneral adults. We also

assessed seasonal differences between the spring and summer generations, revealing shifts in microbial diversity and composition.

A total of 2.2 M paired-end ITS2 reads and 2.7 M of 16S reads were processed. Rarefaction curves confirmed that the sequencing depth was sufficient to capture community diversity. Fungal richness and Shannon diversity were higher in the spring than in the summer ($p < 0.05$), with notable fluctuations observed throughout the life cycle. In contrast, bacterial diversity remained relatively stable across seasons ($p > 0.05$). However, bacterial richness varied by life stage, with the highest diversity found in the larval and pupal stages during spring, while summer samples showed consistent diversity across all stages.

The fungal proportion of the gut microbial community was largely represented by ascomycetous yeasts (Saccharomycetales). The most abundant yeasts were *Wickerhamomyces bisporus*, *Kuraishia molischiana*, and *Nakazawaea ambrosiae*, although their relative proportions differed seasonally. The summer season saw a decrease in *W. bisporus* and an increase in *K. molischiana* and *N. ambrosiae*. The bacterial community was overwhelmingly dominated by Proteobacteria, particularly Enterobacteriales (notably *Erwinia*) and Pseudomonadales (notably *Pseudomonas bohemica*). The diversity of bacterial genera remained relatively stable between seasons, with a marked presence of *Pseudoxanthomonas* in both seasons.

Seasonality and developmental stages strongly influenced the microbial community structure, with significant differences in the mycobiome and bacteriome between parental adults, pupae, and teneral adults ($p < 0.04$). The gut microbiome of parental adults differed significantly from pupal and larval stages, with larval and pupal samples showing higher proportions of yeasts such as *K. molischiana* and *N. ambrosiae*.

In addition to metabarcoding, a traditional cultivation approach was used to isolate microbial strains into pure cultures. We cultured 108 fungal strains representing 13 species, with *Ogataea ramenticola*, *Meyerozyma guilliermondii*, and *W. bisporus* being the most abundant. Bacteria from identic samples were cultivated and published in study (Peral-Aranega, 2020). The results from cultivation confirmed the dominance of yeasts in the gut microbiome and confirmed the findings of metabarcoding. These strains were further identified using ITS rDNA sequencing, providing additional validation for the metagenomic data.

Core Microbiome and Transmission Mechanisms

Our analysis identified a core microbiome of *I. typographus* that persisted throughout the beetle's life cycle and across the seasons. The fungal core microbiome included *Cyberlindnera* sp., *Kuraishia capsulata*, *K. molischiana*, *N. ambrosiae*, *O. neopini*, *O. ramenticola*, *Ophiostoma bicolor*, *Saccharomycopsis lassenensis*, *W. bisporus*, and *Yamadazyma scolyti*, while the bacterial core included *E. typographi*, *E. cedenensis*, *P. bohémica*, *Pseudoxanthomonas spadix*, *Rhizobium* sp., *Curtobacterium* sp., *Roseomonas* sp., *Serratia* sp., *Taibaiella* sp., and unidentified species of the family Sphingobacteriaceae, Lachnospiraceae, and Enterobacteriaceae.

RESEARCH

Open Access

New insight into the bark beetle *ips typographus* bacteriome reveals unexplored diversity potentially beneficial to the host

Ezequiel Peral-Aranega^{1,2*}, Zaki Saati-Santamaría^{1,2,3}, Miguel Ayuso-Calles^{1,2}, Martin Kostovčík³, Tereza Veselská³, Karel Švec³, Raúl Rivas^{1,2,4}, Miroslav Kolařík³ and Paula García-Fraile^{1,2,3,4}

Publication 2 – New insight into the bark beetle *I. typographus* bacteriome reveals unexplored diversity potentially beneficial to the host

Bacteriome Diversity and Taxonomic Composition

We performed a detailed analysis of the bacteriome across the life stages of *I. typographus* (larvae, pupae, teneral adult, and parental adult). The bacteriome was dominated by the phylum *Proteobacteria*, with a notable presence of *Erwinia*, *Pseudomonas*, and *Pseudoxanthomonas* genera. The microbial diversity was highest during the larval phase, with a greater diversity in the adult stage than in the pupae and teneral adults. Unique taxa were detected in specific life stages, such as *Rhizobium* and a *Chitinophagaceae* genus in the teneral adult stage.

Hydrolytic Enzyme Activity and Carbon Assimilation

We assessed the hydrolytic enzyme potential of bacterial isolates from each life stage of the beetle. All strains demonstrated the ability to degrade complex polysaccharides, including

cellulose, pectin, starch, and xylan, providing additional carbon sources for the beetle. The ability to hydrolyze these compounds was strong in particular bacterial strains isolated from larvae and teneral adults, possibly aligning with the stages where beetles need additional nutrition. These enzymes may play a crucial role in helping the beetles break down the rigid plant tissues they encounter.

Antifungal Potential of the Bacteriome

In addition to hydrolytic activity, we evaluated the ability of bacterial strains to antagonize entomopathogenic fungi. The results showed that a majority (83.9 %) of isolates exhibited some degree of antifungal activity, with strains from the genera *Erwinia*, *Pseudomonas*, and *Bacillus* displaying the strongest inhibitory effects. Interestingly, larvae and teneral adults contained strains with the most potent antifungal properties. The detection of siderophore production in many strains also indicates a potential mechanism for competition with other microbes.

Core Bacteriome and Key Microbial Species

The taxonomic analysis revealed that *E. typographi*, *P. bohemica*, and *P. typographi* were consistently present across all life stages, indicating their role as core members of the microbiome. These species, along with *Pseudoxanthomonas* and some undescribed taxa from the Erwiniaceae family, likely contribute significantly to the beetle's fitness by providing nutritional support and protecting it from microbial competitors.

Implications and Future Directions

Our findings underscore the importance of the bacteriome in maintaining the health and survival of *I. typographus*. The metabolic capabilities observed, such as polysaccharide degradation and antifungal activity, suggest that the bacteriome plays a key role in the beetle's ecological fitness. Future studies should focus on a deeper understanding of the interactions between these microbes and the beetle host, as well as exploring the potential for biocontrol applications to mitigate the beetle's impact on forest ecosystems.

OPEN ACCESS

EDITED BY
Yijuan Xu,
South China Agricultural University, China

REVIEWED BY
Ari Mikko Hietala,
Norwegian Institute of Bioeconomy Research
(NIBIO), Norway
Eliane Ferreira Noronha,
University of Brasilia, Brazil

Insight into the genomes of dominant yeast symbionts of European spruce bark beetle, *Ips typographus*

Tian Cheng^{1,2}, Tereza Veselská¹, Barbora Křížková¹, Karel Švec¹,
Václav Havlíček¹, Marc Stadler² and Miroslav Kolařík^{1*}

Publication 3 – Insight into the genomes of dominant yeast symbionts of European spruce bark beetle, *Ips typographus*

Genome Sequencing and Analysis of Yeasts in the *I. typographus* Gut Microbiome

In this study, we sequenced and annotated the genomes of four dominant true yeast species isolated from the gut of *I. typographus* (*K. molischiana*, *N. ambrosiae*, *O. ramenticola*, and *W. bisporus*) and one interesting strain of Basidiomycetous yeast (*Cryptococcus sp.*) (potentially a new species). The genomes revealed between 5,314 and 7,050 protein-coding genes, and GO annotations provided insights into various biological processes, molecular functions, and cellular components. KEGG annotations highlighted key metabolic pathways, including those for essential amino acids and vitamin B6 biosynthesis, critical for beetle nutrition.

Carbohydrate-Active Enzymes (CAZymes) and Plant Cell Wall Degradation

The yeast genomes were examined for carbohydrate-active enzymes (CAZymes) involved in plant cell wall degradation. We identified various classes of CAZymes, including glycoside hydrolases (GH), carbohydrate esterases (CE), and polysaccharide lyases (PL). Among the species, *N. ambrosiae* contained the highest number of CAZymes (221), while *Cryptococcus sp.* Had the fewest (157).

Detoxification Mechanisms in Yeasts

The yeast species possessed a diverse array of detoxification-related enzymes, including cytochrome P450 monooxygenases, aldo-keto reductases, glutathione S-transferases, and ATP-

binding cassette (ABC) transporters. These enzymes play critical roles in the detoxification of plant secondary metabolites, which is vital for the beetles' ability to colonize and degrade host trees. Notably, the yeasts exhibited substantial variation in the number of detoxification genes, with *W. bisporus* containing the most (276 genes) and *Cryptococcus* sp. The least (110 genes). This diverse array of enzymes is indicative of the yeasts' involvement in the complex process of detoxifying plant defences and facilitating beetle nutrition.

Extracellular Enzyme Activities and Functional Implications

In vitro tests assessed the extracellular enzyme activities of the yeasts. The results confirmed the presence of enzymes active in the breakdown of cellulose, Xylan, and pectin, as well as other substrates, including lipids. Among the analyzed yeasts, *K. molischiana* and *N. ambrosiae* had highest activities of cellobiohydrolase and β -glucosidase, the enzymes involved in cellulose degradation. All species, particularly *K. molischiana*, were active in exolytic degradation of hemicellulose. We detected overall low activity in the enzyme affecting pectin degradation. None of the yeasts showed activity against starch, lignin, protein and chitin. *N. ambrosiae* had high acid phosphomonoesterase activity, and together with *W. bisporus*, high lipase activity.

Symbiotic Roles in Nutrient Synthesis and Detoxification

Our findings emphasise the critical role of gut-associated yeasts in the *I. typographus* holobiont. These yeasts contribute to nutrient synthesis (such as essential amino acids and vitamins) and detoxification processes, which are essential for the beetle's survival in a challenging environment. These results suggest a possible metabolic complementarity between the features provided by the yeasts, bacteria, and the beetle itself, facilitating mutual metabolic cooperation and survival in a toxic environment with limited resources.

Metabolic synergy and complementarity in the *Ips typographus* holobiont

Zaki Saati-Santamaría

zakisaati@usal.es

Manuscript 1 – Metabolic synergy and complementarity in the *Ips typographus* holobiont

Metatranscriptome Assembly and Taxonomic Composition

Our metatranscriptomic analysis processed 8,4 M reads in which 602 K ORFs were identified, resulting in 175 K KEGG annotations received. Despite most of the reads belonged to the host beetle (70.6 %), a substantial part was assigned to the microbial community, where Bacteria took 16,8 % and Fungi 6,08 % of total reads. Bacteria were mainly represented by Proteobacteria and Bacillota, Ascomycota predominating in fungal transcripts. Viral transcripts also exhibited high diversity. This analysis underscores the high complexity of *I. typographus*' holobiont and reveals the functional contributions of different kingdoms, especially the significant bacterial and fungal involvement in the beetle's metabolism.

Functional Diversity and Holobiont Complementarity

Despite the dominance of the beetle's transcriptome in the dataset, bacteria and fungi contribute equally to the overall functional diversity within the holobiont. The PERMANOVA analysis revealed significant differences in life stages ($p = 0.004$), though the variability within groups was greater than between life stages, especially between larvae and adult beetles. This indicates that the microbial community plays a more pivotal role than life-stage-specific variations in shaping the functional outputs of the holobiont.

Microbial Contributions to Degradation of Plant and Fungal Cell Wall Polymers

A key function of microbial symbionts is the degradation of complex plant and fungal cell wall polymers, including chitin, glucan, mannan, cellulose, and hemicellulose. These processes are vital for the beetle's nutrition, as they facilitate the energy uptake from plant material

and fungal cell walls. Our data indicate that while bacterial gut symbionts play a dominant role in polymer degradation, the entire holobiont participates in completing these complex metabolic processes. For instance, chitin degradation is facilitated by both the beetle and its microbial partners, with similar contributions from fungi and bacteria. Bacteria initiate Xylan and pectin degradation, but beetle and fungi further support these processes. Lignin degradation is primarily bacterial, with eukaryotes utilizing by-products. Notably, the bacterial taxa *Erwinia*, *Delftia*, and *Phyllobacterium* drive most of these catabolic activities. On the other hand, Ascomycota, particularly *Ogataea* yeast, contribute to glucan degradation, while the beetle helps to facilitate cellulose breakdown.

Nitrogen Utilization within the Holobiont

Nitrogen acquisition is critical for the beetle, given the nitrogen-limited environment in *Picea abies* phloem. Our results show that bacterial symbionts facilitate nitrogen acquisition, primarily through nitrate reduction to ammonia. The beetle's microbiota also contributes to the conversion of uric acid into usable nitrogen sources, such as ammonia. Bacterial taxa like *Delftia*, *Erwinia*, and *Cupriavidus* are key players in this process. Fungi seem to rely on the ammonia produced by bacteria, scavenging it rather than contributing directly to ammonia conversion. This nitrogen cycle illustrates the essential role of microbial collaboration in overcoming the beetle's nutritional constraints.

Cross-Kingdom Cooperation in Amino Acid Metabolism

Our analysis further revealed the intricate cooperation between beetle, bacteria, and fungi in amino acid metabolism. Essential amino acids such as histidine and lysine are synthesized by bacteria, with fungi playing a supporting role. However, the beetle largely depends on its symbiotic microbes for the synthesis of amino acids such as branched-chain amino acids (valine, leucine, isoleucine) and phenylalanine. This highlights the interdependence of the beetle and its microbial partners in synthesizing and interconverting amino acids. Notably, bacterial taxa such as *Erwinia*, *Delftia*, and *Phyllobacterium*, as well as fungal taxa like Sordariomycetes (including *Ophiostoma*), are key contributors to these pathways.

Vitamin Co-Metabolism in the Holobiont

Our data also shed light on the complex division of labor in vitamin co-metabolism within the holobiont. Microbial symbionts, particularly bacteria and fungi, contribute significantly to the biosynthesis of essential vitamins such as folate (B9), biotin (B7), and vitamins B3, B5, B2, B1, and B6. For example, folate biosynthesis is primarily driven by bacteria, with fungi and beetle

scavenging and utilizing the by-products. Similarly, biotin synthesis is largely bacterial, with beetle and fungi recycling biotin from biocytin. We suggest that particular bacteria play an important role in the metabolism of several vitamins, with bacteria and fungi providing essential precursors and modifications. This metabolic network ensures that the beetle's nutritional needs are met, further emphasizing the cooperative nature of the beetle holobiont.

Conclusion

The metatranscriptomic data reveals a highly integrated and cooperative system within the bark beetle holobiont, where bacteria, fungi, and the beetle itself complement each other's metabolic functions. The beetle relies on its microbial symbionts for essential processes such as degradation of complex polymers, nitrogen utilization, amino acid biosynthesis, and vitamin metabolism. The findings underscore the importance of cross-kingdom cooperation in sustaining the nutritional and metabolic needs of the holobiont, offering a deeper understanding of the functional roles of its microbial partners. The interplay between the beetle and its microbiota is a key factor in its survival and adaptation in its ecological niche.

Organ specificity in taxonomically related ash bark beetles is accompanied by the specific microbial communities –

Křížková Barbora¹, Martin Kostovčík¹, Karel Švec¹, Oto Nakládál², Miroslav Kolařík^{1*}

Manuscript 2 - Organ specificity in taxonomically related ash bark beetles is accompanied by specific microbial communities

Diversity and Taxonomic Composition

We investigated the total microbial communities associated with two closely related Ash bark beetle species, *H. fraxini* (infesting thin branches) and *H. crenatus* (infesting tree trunks), using a combination of NGS metabarcoding (markers: 16S, ITS, TEF1α) and cultivation approaches. Across all datasets, we obtained over 3 million sequencing reads and characterized 134 fungal species from cultivation. Rarefaction analyses indicated near-complete sampling, particularly for beetle-associated samples, though intact phloem samples were slightly under-sampled.

Bacterial communities were dominated by Proteobacteria, Bacteroidota, and Actinobacteria, with beetle samples harboring mainly Enterobacterales and intact phloem showing greater

taxonomic diversity. Fungal communities were strongly dominated by Ascomycota across beetles and phloem, with some Basidiomycota more prevalent in *H. fraxini* samples.

Distinct fungal communities were linked to the beetle species:

H. crenatus primarily associated with Saccharomycetales and Ophiostomatales (e.g., *Ophiostoma hylesinum* and *Ogataea* spp.). *H. fraxini* exhibited a broader fungal community, including *Geosmithia* spp., *Candida* spp., and other diverse fungi, with almost no Ophiostomatales detected.

Cultivation data confirmed metabarcoding results but also revealed a significant fraction of undescribed fungal taxa (particularly among yeasts). Bacterial taxa such as *Erwinia* spp. and Sphingobacteriaceae were characteristic for beetle tissue samples, while *Hymenobacter* and *Sphingomonas* dominated control samples (phloem).

Community Structure and Differentiation

Beta-diversity analyses (Robust Aitchison PCA made in DEICODE toolbox) clearly separated microbial communities of *H. crenatus* and *H. fraxini* based on fungi and bacteria, with dominant fungal species such as *O. hylesinum* and *Geosmithia flava* significantly influencing differentiation. Larval and both tunneling and overwintering adult stages showed consistent symbiont profiles, but larvae displayed lower fungal biodiversity than adults.

Physiological Adaptations of Symbiotic Fungi

We examined physiological traits of key fungi under varying abiotic conditions.

pH tolerance: *O. hylesinum* preferred more acidic conditions (optimum pH 4), whereas *Geosmithia* species tolerated wider pH ranges, favoring slightly neutral conditions.

Osmotolerance: *Geosmithia* species showed higher salt tolerance compared to Ophiostomatales.

Temperature: No significant difference between groups; most fungi grew optimally at 25–30°C.

Oxygen levels: All tested species preferred low-oxygen (microaerophilic) conditions.

Tolerance to plant secondary metabolites: Most fungi grew well with condensed tannins and flavonoids, but tannic acid inhibited many strains except *G. flava*.

Conclusion

Despite living on the same host tree, *H. fraxini* and *H. crenatus* maintain distinct microbial communities. Our experimental results suggest that the ecological differentiation of their symbionts may be linked to microhabitat-specific abiotic factors, particularly pH and water availability, rather than solely to beetle-mediated selection. Our findings highlight the complex interplay of host organ specificity, environment, and microbial physiology in shaping beetle-associated microbiomes.

General discussion

The specific requirements of life under the bark and the choice of a suitable model species

When bark beetles enter the environment beneath tree bark, they encounter a challenging habitat characterized by hard-to-degrade polysaccharides, toxic plant secondary metabolites, insufficient amount of essential nutrients required for their development and often an oxygen-poor atmosphere combined with rapidly fluctuating temperatures and water activity levels (Boone et al., 2013; Gandhi & Hofstetter, 2021; García-Fraile, 2018; Hagen, 2002; Linnakoski et al., 2017; Morales-Jiménez et al., 2012b). Additionally, they face competition from numerous microorganisms that also rely on the limited available nutrients. To successfully colonize host trees, bark beetles form symbiotic relationships with diverse microbial communities (Biedermann & Vega, 2020).

The European spruce bark beetle, *I. typographus*, is a major pest of spruce trees in the Palearctic region. This aggressive bark beetle causes the notorious outbreaks in silvicultures throughout Europe, causing enormous economic losses (Hlásny et al., 2021a, 2021b). Furthermore, it can be assumed that climate change will further intensify the impact of bark beetles on forest ecosystems (Biedermann et al., 2019a; García-Fraile, 2018). As a result of its socio-economic impact on human communities, it has a significant effect on the environment, thus subsequent attention of the scientific community; its genome is already available (Powell et al., 2021) and transcriptome as well (Ramakrishnan et al., 2022). Although previous research has explored the microbial communities associated with this beetle species (Chakraborty, Ashraf, et al., 2020; Chakraborty, Modlinger, et al., 2020a; Fabryová et al., 2018; Fang et al., 2020; Moussa et al., 2024), our study is the first comprehensive description of both bacterial and fungal gut microbiota across the beetle's entire developmental cycle and spanning two successive generations.

In contrast to *Ips*, *Hylesinus* represents a chronically understudied genus of bark beetles from hardwoods. Regardless of its unexplored nature, *H. crenatus* and *H. faxini* represent an ideal species pair for answering the fundamental ecological questions related to the microhabitat adaptations through a specific symbiotic microbiota (Strzałka et al., 2021).

Observed microbial diversity

Our results revealed low microbial α -diversity within the intestinal community of bark beetles, a pattern commonly observed in bark beetle-associated microbiota (Barcoto et al., 2020; Briones-Roblero et al., 2017). In agreement with findings reported by (Chakraborty, Modlinger, et al., 2020a, 2020b) and (Baños-Quintana et al., 2024; Fang et al., 2020), our data confirmed the dominance of Gammaproteobacteria-Enterobacterales (namely *E. typographi*, *P. bohémica*, and *P. typographi*) within the bacterial microbiome of *I. typographus*. Although the previous studies (Chakraborty, Ashraf, et al., 2020; Chakraborty, Modlinger, et al., 2020a performed in Rouchovany, Czechia) and (Fang et al., 2020 performed in Jingouling Forest Farm, China) used different region of the rRNA region for metabarcoding, our studies sampled in Křivoklátsko Protected Landscape Area, Czech Republic, targeted the V5–V6 region. This methodological difference may introduce biases in taxonomic resolution and community composition (Claesson et al., 2010). Interestingly, a potentially novel genus within the order Enterobacterales was consistently detected across all developmental stages in our dataset and was also reported in (Fang et al., 2020). It should be noted that (Fang et al., 2020) did not include teneral adults in their analysis and separated adult males and females. Despite these differences, they similarly observed a high abundance of *Erwinia* during the larval stage, which declined during pupation, whereas *Pseudoxanthomonas* showed the opposite trend. In contrast, (Chakraborty, Ashraf, et al., 2020) reported *Rahnella* and *Raoultella* as dominant taxa, neither of which were detected in our amplicon data, nor did they report the potentially undescribed Enterobacterales genus found in our study. However, genera such as *Pseudomonas*, *Acinetobacter*, and *Streptococcus* were consistently detected across all studies (Chakraborty, Ashraf, et al., 2020; Fang et al., 2020). Based on recently published works (Baños-Quintana et al., 2024; Chakraborty et al., 2023; Khara et al., 2024; Moussa et al., 2024) all following the publication of our studies, we can conclude that a similar bacterial community was found to be associated with *I. typographus* on a very large geographic area, which may indicate the stability of this symbiosis.

The fungal community was primarily composed of yeasts belonging to the class Saccharomycetes, predominantly Genera (*Kuraishia*, *Nakazawaea*, *Wickerhamomyces*, *Ogataea*) and Cryptococcus from class Tremellomycetes, followed by filamentous fungi from

class Sordariomycetes, particularly species known as symbiotic partners of *I. typographus*, such as *Ophiostoma bicolor* and *Endoconidiophora polonica* (R. Jankowiak, 2005; Linnakoski et al., 2012; Repe et al., 2013a).

While DNA-based metabarcoding and cultivation experiments primarily identified members of the class Gammaproteobacteria, our RNA-based metabarcoding approach additionally emphasized the significant presence and activity of Betaproteobacteria, Actinomycetia, and Alphaproteobacteria. Specifically, the genera *Klebsiella*, *Enterobacter*, and *Phyllobacterium* emerged as the most metabolically active taxa according to RNA metabarcoding results. Although fungal community composition appeared consistent between DNA and RNA metabarcoding analyses, significant discrepancies were observed within the bacterial microbiome. These differences may reflect the well-documented concept that species abundance does not necessarily correlate with functional activity or dominance (Risely, 2020).

Enterobacter and *Erwinia* strains have previously been isolated from other bark beetle species, including the important species of the *Dendroctonus valens* (Morales-Jiménez et al., 2009). Similarly, family Enterobacteriaceae is reported to be a major bacterium in the *Dendroctonus rhizophagus* gut (Morales-Jiménez et al., 2012b). To the best of our knowledge, the presence or potential functional role of *Phyllobacterium* spp. has not yet been documented in bark beetles. However, this genus is frequently identified as an endophyte in plants, with certain strains capable of promoting the growth of *Picea* sp. (Anand et al., 2007). Future research should therefore explore the metabolic activities and ecological roles of these microbes within the *I. typographus* holobiont.

Identifying the core microbiome of *I. typographus*

Although the composition of the intestinal microbiome undergoes substantial changes during the lifecycle and across generations of *I. typographus*, we identified a stable core community consistently present in the beetle gut. This core microbiome includes yeast species such as *Cyberlindnera* sp., *K. molischiana*, *K. capsulata*, *N. ambrosiae*, *W. bisporus*, *O. ramenticola*, *Ogataea neopini*, *S. lassenensis*, and *Y. scolyti*, as well as the filamentous fungus *O. bicolor*. Among bacteria, we detected the consistent presence of *E. typographi*, *E. cedenensis*, *Pseudomonas bohémica*, *Pseudoxanthomonas spadix*, and strains from genera *Curtobacterium*, *Roseomonas*, *Serratia*, *Taibaiella*, and other unidentified species belonging to the families Sphingobacteriaceae, Lachnospiraceae, and Enterobacteriaceae. Most of these core microbial taxa have already been reported as associates of various bark beetle species, suggesting their

widespread occurrence in bark beetle habitats (Baños-Quintana et al., 2024; Barcoto et al., 2020; Briones-Roblero et al., 2017; Chakraborty, Ashraf, et al., 2020; Chakraborty et al., 2023; Chakraborty, Modlinger, et al., 2020a; García-Fraile, 2018; Giordano et al., 2013; Hernández-García et al., 2018; Linnakoski et al., 2021; Lou et al., 2014; Moussa et al., 2024; Saati-Santamaría et al., 2018, 2021). These results suggest that a stable core of gut microbiome (bacteria and fungi) persists throughout *I. typographus* development, providing essential metabolic support regardless of environmental fluctuation.

In some plant-feeding insects, including bark beetles, the gut microbiome is very specific and resistant to changes (Adams et al., 2013b). In others, the microbiome changes more frequently, mostly based on their diet, and can differ between insect populations (Adams et al., 2010; Jones et al., 2019; Šigut et al., 2022). This variability suggests that insects pick up their gut microbes directly from the environment (Kikuchi et al., 2007). We propose that the core gut microbiome of *I. typographus* originates from microbes naturally living inside healthy spruce phloem - the beetle's main food source.

Our analysis of α -diversity (Shannon index) and cultured bacterial communities in (Peral-Aranega et al., 2023) showed that the composition of the *I. typographus* bacteriome changes across its life stages. Bacterial diversity was highest in larvae, decreased in pupae, remained low in teneral adults, and increased again in mature adults. This pattern was not always observed in our other study (Veselská et al., 2023) or (Fang et al., 2020), but it is similar to what has been reported in *Dendroctonus rhizophagus*, although teneral adults were not included in that study (Morales-Jiménez et al., 2012a). We hypothesized that these changes are likely caused by metamorphosis, which alters the gut environment and affects which bacteria can survive. However, some bacterial taxa were present in all stages, suggesting they may play important roles throughout development. Most of the bacteria found in *I. typographus* are likely acquired from the phloem; however, it is also possible that some are passed from adults to their offspring, as observed in other insect species (Baños-Quintana et al., 2024; Bright & Bulgheresi, 2010).

Acquisition and Localization of Gut Symbionts

At the same time, our TEM analysis did not reveal any specialized microbial structures or biofilm formation in the gut of *I. typographus*, which may indicate that microorganisms are likely transiently passing through the digestive tract along with plant material rather than being permanently retained. Therefore, we suggest that the gut microbiome of *I. typographus* is predominantly acquired from ingested plant tissues, with environmental filtering favoring microbial taxa adapted to survive under the harsh gut conditions (Appel & Maines, 1995; Douglas,

2014; Engel & Moran, 2013). Further feeding experiments would be valuable to test this hypothesis. An exception to this general pattern was observed for the mutualistic filamentous fungi *O. bicolor* and *Endoconidiophora polonica* (B. R. Jankowiak, 2005; R. Jankowiak et al., 2009; Linnakoski et al., 2016; Repe et al., 2013b), whose proportions in the gut microbiome increased progressively throughout the beetle's development. This trend suggests microbial succession analogous to that documented in other insects, e.g. galleries of the ambrosia beetle *Xyleborus affinis* (Ibarra-Juarez et al., 2020), where initial colonizers such as bacteria and yeasts are gradually replaced or supplemented by filamentous fungi. Both *O. bicolor* and *E. polonica* are actively transported by bark beetles into new host trees (Biedermann et al., 2019c), aligning with our observations of their relatively low abundance in intact spruce phloem compared to their increased presence in phloem adjacent to bark beetle galleries by the end of the beetle's development.

Metabolic complementarity within the *I. typographus* holobiont

Our previous studies have shown that the gut-associated bacterial and fungal symbionts of *I. typographus* possess genomic potential for nutrient provisioning, detoxification, and complex carbohydrate degradation (Cheng et al., 2023; Fabryová et al., 2018; Veselská et al., 2023). (Fabryová et al., 2018) is not part of this dissertation, but it is also a publication performed by our broader team. However, the level to which these microbes interact functionally as a cooperative system remained unresolved. In this dissertation, we build on these foundational insights and present the first metatranscriptomic evidence for metabolic complementarity among the members of the *I. typographus* holobiont (Saati-Santamaría et al. 2025, unpubl. -here referred to as "Manuscript 1").

These analyses revealed a pronounced division of labor among bacterial and fungal taxa: bacterial symbionts such as *Erwinia*, *Delftia*, and *Phyllobacterium* were transcriptionally active in pathways involved in nitrogen cycling - specifically nitrate/nitrite reduction and uric acid catabolism, while fungal taxa, including *Ogataea* and *Kuraishia*, contributed to urea and ammonia assimilation (Saati-Santamaría et al. 2025, unpubl.-here referred to as "Manuscript 1"). This functional pattern reflects a cross-kingdom interdependence, where metabolic products from one group serve as substrates for another. While such microbial cooperation was previously hypothesized in gallery biofilms (Barcoto et al., 2020; Ibarra-Juarez et al., 2020), our study provides the first functional evidence for this integration at the gut level.

Moreover, our metatranscriptomic results confirm and extend genome-based predictions from our genomic study of yeast symbionts (Cheng et al., 2023), which demonstrated the presence

of biosynthetic pathways for vitamin B6 and essential amino acids, but according to the transcriptome, they rely on intermediates from bacteria. Perhaps this is because they “save” and take what is in excess from the environment. We also observed that bacterial taxa were transcriptionally active in biosynthetic pathways for thiamine (B1), riboflavin (B2), biotin (B7), and pyridoxal derivatives. At the same time, yeasts appeared to complement or scavenge these intermediates (Saati-Santamaría et al., unpubl.). These observations are further supported by enzymatic assays from our culture-based study (Peral-Aranega et al., 2023), which demonstrated that strains of *Pseudomonas* and *Bacillus* exhibited strong hydrolytic and antifungal activity against bacterial isolates across various stages of beetle development. The yeast strains examined according to sequenced genomes should be capable of breaking down pectin, but our *in vitro* tests did not confirm this ability, or only inconclusively. Filamentous fungal symbionts are known to break down cellulose, which has been confirmed by our transcriptomic data, unlike pectin, which in our system is probably degraded only mostly by bacteria. Among other things, this shows that the presence of a pathway in the fungal genome may not always manifest itself under *in vivo* conditions, as observed, for example, in the work of (Kjærboelling et al., 2020).

Our transcriptomic findings also align with previous work highlighting the dynamic nature of the *I. typographus* gut microbiome (Veselská et al., 2023), where temporal shifts in taxonomic composition were observed but masked potential functional redundancy among community members. The current metatranscriptomic dataset resolves this ambiguity by showing that taxa differ in abundance may still contribute consistently to critical functions.

Taken together, these results demonstrate that the *I. typographus* holobiont functions not merely as a host-associated microbial assemblage, but as an ecologically and metabolically integrated consortium. This organization likely confers adaptive advantages in the nutrient-limited and chemically defended phloem environment (Zhao et al., 2019). It represents a model of microbial synergy with relevance beyond bark beetle systems.

Gut microbiome benefits – direct study approaches

While metatranscriptomic results revealed functionally active metabolic interactions, we further validated the ecological potential of bacterial symbionts through *in vitro* functional assays. Only a limited number of studies have investigated the composition and ecological significance of the bacterial community associated with the bark beetle *I. typographus*. In our studies, we examine the diversity of the beetle’s bacteriome across different developmental stages by integrating data from both cultured isolates and metabarcoding analyses. Furthermore, we performed *in vitro* experiments to assess the metabolic capabilities of the isolated strains

and to explore their potential contributions to the beetle's ecological interactions, dynamics and functional redundancy in the gut microbiome across the life cycle of *I. typographus* (Cheng et al., 2023).

We observed considerable shifts in the overall microbial composition throughout the developmental stages of *I. typographus*. Some fungi showed increased abundance at specific life stages; for example, yeasts *K. molischiana* and *N. ambrosiae* dominated during larval and pupal stages, while *S. lassenensis* was more abundant in parental adults. Additionally, spring adult beetles exhibited a high proportion of unique ASVs. Since *I. typographus* adults may overwinter beneath the bark or in forest litter, this could temporarily enrich their gut microbiome with microbial species originating from environments beyond spruce phloem. However, these externally acquired microorganisms seem to diminish or disappear during subsequent developmental phases. We also recorded a reduction in the number of fungal ASVs in larvae and pupae compared to parental adults and teneral stages. A similar decline has previously been noted by (Lou et al., 2014) in yeasts associated with the bark beetle *Dendroctonus valens*, and by (González-Serrano et al., 2020) in bacteria from the moth *Brithys crini*. The initial fungal diversity decrease at the larval stage may reflect the loss of parental adult-transmitted microbes originating from previous hosts, whereas the second reduction during the pupal stage might be linked to physiological changes accompanying metamorphosis and reformation of the gut (González-Serrano et al., 2020). Furthermore, seasonality had a significant influence on the microbial community structure. Seasonal variations primarily affected the relative proportions of dominant microbial taxa rather than their presence or absence. The filamentous fungi associated with *I. typographus* likely share similar functional roles, such as detoxifying plant-derived secondary metabolites, making them functionally interchangeable (Zhao et al., 2019). Consequently, in agreement with (Bang-Andreasen et al., 2019; R. Jankowiak, 2005; Louca et al., 2017) we propose that *I. typographus* associates with functionally similar microbial taxa, whose community composition and structure are primarily shaped by environmental conditions (Banos, 2024; Chakraborty, 2024).

We also investigated the potential ecological functions of the isolated bacterial strains concerning two key aspects of *I. typographus* biology: digestion of complex carbon sources and protection against fungal entomopathogens, both traditionally assumed to be benefits mediated by bacteria (Peral-Aranega et al., 2023). Several bacterial isolates demonstrated the ability to hydrolyze CMC, xylan, pectin, and starch, all of which are components of the inner bark (Peral-Aranega et al., 2020, 2023, Saati-Santamaría et al. 2025, unpubl. -here referred as “Manuscript 1”). Notably, *Bacillus tequilensis* and *P. typographi* strains isolated from larvae and adults

exhibited strong hydrolytic activity across all tested polysaccharides. In addition, 32 other strains belonging to the genera *Erwinia*, *Bacillus*, *Pseudomonas*, *Paenibacillus*, and *Curtobacterium* were capable of hydrolyzing three out of the four tested polysaccharides (all except xylan). These findings are consistent with previous reports on *Ips*-associated bacteria that produce enzymes capable of breaking down complex plant polysaccharides into simpler sugars accessible for bark beetles (Fabryová et al., 2018; Peral-Aranega, 2020). This pattern is consistent with earlier findings discussed above (see Observed microbial diversity), particularly regarding the dominance of *Pseudomonas* and Enterobacteriaceae taxa throughout the beetle's development.

Bark excavation by *I. typographus* occurs during both the adult phase (establishing the gallery) and the larval stage (feeding in the gallery), which aligns with the life stages from which the most active hydrolytic strains were isolated. Our data also suggests that bacterial isolates from adult beetles tend to show higher hydrolytic capacities. (Peral-Aranega, 2020).

In addition, amplicon sequencing revealed the exclusive presence of a putative novel bacterial genus within the Chitinophagaceae family in teneral adults. This family includes genera known to degrade chitin, a key component of fungal cell walls and insect exoskeletons (Carter et al., 2015; Muthukrishnan et al., 2020). During the teneral adult stage, the beetle cuticle is still developing and progressively thickens (Banskar et al., 2016). Concurrently, fungal sporulation often occurs within pupal chambers, and teneral adults may acquire these fungi during feeding (Six, 2012). These findings correspond with our studies (Peral-Aranega et al., 2023) and observations of (Veselská et al., 2023), where we reported the lowest fungal ASV abundance in pupae and a subsequent increase in teneral adults. This may explain the appearance of Chitinophagaceae at this particular life stage.

Furthermore, we found that strains from the Erwiniaceae family and the genera *Pseudomonas*, *Bacillus*, *Staphylococcus*, *Streptomyces*, *Acinetobacter*, and *Brevundimonas* produced siderophores, iron-chelating compounds that may confer competitive advantages by limiting iron availability to other microbes (Pažoutová et al., 2010). Notably, the first four genera have previously been shown to produce siderophores with antifungal activity (Nagpure et al., 2014; Raaska & Mattila-Sandholm, 1995; Sulochana et al., 2014; Wilson et al., 2006; Yu et al., 2011). Strains from these genera, along with a *Nocardiodes* isolate, exhibited strong antifungal activity against eight strains of entomopathogenic fungi (*Lecanicillium muscarium*, *Beauveria brongniartii*, *Metarhizium anisopliae*, *L. muscarium*, *Isaria farinose*, *I. fumosorosea* and 2 strains of *B. bassiana*), suggesting the production of antifungal bioactive compounds. Several of these genera are already known to synthesize such compounds (Alijani et al., 2019; El-Goorani et al.,

1992; Liu et al., 2007; Prapagdee et al., 2008), including a non-polyene antifungal compound isolated from *Streptomyces albidoflavus* (Augustine et al., 2005).

Interestingly, the most potent antifungal strains were isolated from larvae, which is consistent with the increased vulnerability of this life stage to fungal pathogens (Erler & Ates, 2015). However, the highest frequency of strains showing strong antifungal activity was recorded in adult beetles.

Mycobiome benefits – Genomic study of *I. typographus* major fungal symbionts

Although the fungal community of *I. typographus* has been studied for many years by cultivation methods, new fungal associates continue to be discovered by NGS (Jankowiak & Bilański, 2018; Linnakoski et al., 2016). Recent research, including our work, has demonstrated both spatial and temporal variation in fungal assemblages (Linnakoski et al., 2016; Netherer et al., 2021) and has shown that volatile organic compounds can influence interactions between the beetle and its fungal partners (Zhao et al., 2019). Traditionally, research has focused on ectosymbiotic filamentous fungi, which grow extensively in and around beetle galleries and often cause visible discoloration of plant tissue or exhibit plant pathogenic traits. *Endoconidiophora polonica* and *O. bicolor*, along with *Ceratocystis penicillata* and *Grosmannia europheoides*, are well-known filamentous symbionts of *I. typographus* that contribute to overcoming host tree defenses (Netherer et al., 2021; Zhao et al., 2019). Although yeasts are now recognized as regular components of bark beetle gut microbiota (Rivera et al., 2009; Davis, 2015), including in *I. typographus* (Chakraborty et al., 2020) and also as our work has confirmed, they were largely overlooked in earlier studies due to challenges in their taxonomic identification, lack of phytopathogenic effects and their overall cryptic and elusive nature.

In our study (Cheng et al., 2023), we sequenced and annotated the genomes of several yeast species to explore their potential roles within the *I. typographus* gut microbiome. Bark beetles encounter challenging conditions when colonizing tree tissues as described above. Filamentous fungi associated with bark beetles are known to assist in this process by contributing to detoxification and often inducing necrosis in plant tissues (Hofstetter et al., 2015; Li et al., 2022; Zhao et al., 2019). CAzymes are key in breaking down complex plant polysaccharides such as lignocellulose (Arntzen et al., 2020; Chettri et al., 2020). Our genome analyses of five yeast species revealed the presence of a range of CAzyme-encoding genes, representing approximately 3.6% of the predicted proteins. This proportion is comparable to levels found in phytopathogenic fungi associated with bark beetles, such as *Ophiostoma novo-ulmi* (Comeau et al., 2015) and

Grosmannia clavigera (DiGuistini et al., 2011), but is lower than that reported for other members of Pezizomycotina (Comeau et al., 2015).

Our *in vitro* assays showed that these yeasts do not possess endolytic enzymes capable of degrading lignocellulose, which limits their ability to break down these complex polymers directly. However, they do produce exolytic enzymes that cleave pectin and act on terminal carbohydrate residues, enabling them to utilize simpler sugars. These findings are consistent with previous studies by (Barcoto et al., 2020) and (Ibarra-Juarez et al., 2020) which demonstrated that bacteria in bark beetle galleries have a higher capacity than fungi for degrading structural plant components. These studies also suggest that the beetle holobiont forms a cooperative biofilm where microbial species can benefit from one another's enzymatic activities.

In addition to CAzymes, genes involved in oxidative stress response and detoxification play key roles in fungal colonization of plant tissues (Comeau et al., 2015; DiGuistini et al., 2011; Schuelke et al., 2017). The analyzed yeasts possess several such genes, including aldo-keto reductases, glutathione S-transferases, cytochrome P450 monooxygenases (CYPs), carboxylesterases, and flavin-containing monooxygenases, enzymes known to break down toxic plant compounds. They also encode transporters involved in stress and drug resistance, such as ABC transporters and members of the MFS and MATE families.

All six identified CYP subfamilies have been previously reported in yeast genomes (Linder, 2019). Among them, CYP51, CYP61, and CYP56 are essential for growth, contributing to ergosterol biosynthesis and spore wall formation. CYP52 is involved in alkane and fatty acid metabolism, while the functions of CYP501 and CYP5252 remain unknown. Interestingly, *I. typographus* also carries genes related to detoxification (Naseer et al., 2023), raising questions about the interaction and potential complementarity of insect and microbial detoxification pathways.

Fungal symbionts not only aid in colonizing plant tissues but may also contribute to beetle nutrition. Due to the low nitrogen content of plant tissues (Yang & Luo, 2011), larvae must bore long tunnels to meet their needs. Symbiotic fungi improve nitrogen availability in galleries, enhancing beetle fitness (Ayres et al., 2000). All yeasts examined in this genome sequencing experiment possess pathways for the biosynthesis of essential amino acids and vitamin B6, which the insect must obtain from its diet (Arora & Douglas, 2017), indicating their potential nutritional contribution.

In summary, genome analysis of five gut-associated yeast isolates *K. molischiana*, *Cryptococcus* sp., *N. ambrosiae*, *O. ramenticola*, and *W. bisporus* reveals the ability of these major *I. typographus* symbionts to provide the essential nutrients and produce detoxification-related

enzymes. Although they cannot degrade lignocellulose directly, they may benefit from breakdown products generated by other microorganisms. The genomic data presented here enhances our understanding of the functional roles of gut yeasts in the *I. typographus* holobiont.

Ecological filtering and symbiont divergence in 2 non-mycangial Ash bark beetles

In addition to the well-characterized symbiosis of *Ips typographus*, our comparative study of two ash-infesting bark beetles—*Hylesinus crenatus* and *H. fraxini*—provides novel insights into how habitat conditions influence fungal community composition in non-mycangial species, i.e., beetles lacking specialized symbiont-carrying organs. Although both beetles feed on *Fraxinus excelsior*, they exploit different tree parts: *H. crenatus* lives beneath thick, moist trunk bark, while *H. fraxini* colonizes thinner, more exposed and less stable microhabitats of tree branches.

Following earlier observations (Strzalka 2021), who were the first to suggest a strong ecological partitioning between *H. crenatus* and ophiostomatoid fungi versus *H. fraxini* and *Geosmithia* spp., we hypothesized that these beetles form symbioses with fungal taxa adapted to their respective microhabitats. Our data confirmed this expectation: *H. crenatus* was consistently associated with *O. hylesinum* and Saccharomycetales yeasts, while *H. fraxini* harbored diverse *Geosmithia* spp., accompanied again with various Saccharomycetales yeasts, as dominant fungal partners (Křížková et al., unpubl-Manuscript 2.).

This separation is not merely taxonomic but reflects distinct physiological tolerances. Our *in vitro* screening revealed that *Geosmithia* isolates are tolerant to higher pH levels, osmotic stress, and inhibitory compounds such as tannic acid, suggesting adaptation to drier, chemically more complex environments. In contrast, *O. hylesinum* preferred lower pH and moist conditions, consistent with its dominance under thick bark where desiccation is limited. These physiological profiles support the idea that fungal symbionts, like their insect hosts, possess ecological niches defined by abiotic filtering (Křížková et al., unpubl.-Manuscript 2).

Our findings are further corroborated by (Williams & Ginzl, 2021), who demonstrated that *G. morbida* has a competitive advantage in low-moisture environments, potentially explaining outbreak dynamics in *Juglans nigra*. Taken together, these studies show that fungal symbionts are not passive passengers, but ecologically specialized partners whose habitat filtering mirrors that of their beetle hosts.

Simplified Conclusions

- Despite the absence of specialized transmission structures, *I. typographus* has a core gut microbial community which is largely stable throughout its whole life cycle and between generations.
- The core gut microbiome of *I. typographus* is composed mainly from Saccharomycetous yeasts and bacteria belonging to Enterobacteriales.
- The gut microbiome of *I. typographus* exhibits pronounced metabolic complementarity, which together compensate metabolic deficiencies in the beetle.
- Metabolic pathway redundancy among symbionts indicates functional resilience.
- In the absence of nitrogen fixation, the microbial community relies on recycling nitrogen through nitrate reduction and uric acid degradation. Bacteria thereby provide assimilable nitrogen in the form of ammonia, which supports de novo synthesis of organic nitrogenous compounds by both symbionts and the host.
- Ammonia serves as a central “nitrogen currency” within the holobiont of *I. typographus*. It is a product of oxidizing of inorganic nitrogen form made by bacteria and organic nitrogen cycling from the beetle waste product facilitated by bacteria and fungi.
- Closely related *Hylesinus* species inhabiting different parts of the same tree harbor distinct fungal communities, reflecting organ-specific niche filtering.
- Two *Hylesinus* species harbor species-specific fungal communities despite sharing the same host tree and locality.
- Physiological experiments confirmed that dominant fungal symbionts of *Hylesinus* beetles exhibit niche-specific tolerance to abiotic stress

Funding

I would like to thank the GAUK and GAČR grant agencies, and European Commission for their financial support of our research, specifically projects GAUK 380 021, GACR 16-15293Y, and Horizon 2020 RISE MCSA 101008129 (Mycobiomycs).

References

- Adams, A. S., Adams, S. M., Currie, C. R., Gillette, N. E., & Raffa, K. F. (2010). Geographic variation in bacterial communities associated with the red turpentine beetle (Coleoptera: Curculionidae). *Environmental Entomology*, *39*(2), 406–414.
<https://doi.org/10.1603/EN09221>
- Adams, A. S., Aylward, F. O., Adams, S. M., Erbilgin, N., Aukema, B. H., Currie, C. R., Suen, G., & Raffa, K. F. (2013a). Mountain pine beetles colonizing historical and naïve host trees are associated with a bacterial community highly enriched in genes contributing to terpene metabolism. *Applied and Environmental Microbiology*, *79*(11), 3468–3475.
<https://doi.org/10.1128/AEM.00068-13>
- Adams, A. S., Aylward, F. O., Adams, S. M., Erbilgin, N., Aukema, B. H., Currie, C. R., Suen, G., & Raffa, K. F. (2013b). Mountain pine beetles colonizing historical and naïve host trees are associated with a bacterial community highly enriched in genes contributing to terpene metabolism. *Applied and Environmental Microbiology*, *79*(11), 3468–3475.
<https://doi.org/10.1128/AEM.00068-13>
- Alijani, Z., Amini, J., Ashengroph, M., & Bahramnejad, B. (2019). Antifungal activity of volatile compounds produced by *Staphylococcus sciuri* strain MarR44 and its potential for the biocontrol of *Colletotrichum nymphaeae*, causal agent strawberry anthracnose. *International Journal of Food Microbiology*, *307*(April), 108276.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijfoodmicro.2019.108276>
- Allwood, A. C., Walter, M. R., Burch, I. W., & Kamber, B. S. (2007). 3.43 billion-year-old stromatolite reef from the Pilbara Craton of Western Australia: Ecosystem-scale insights to early life on Earth. *Precambrian Research*, *158*(3–4), 198–227.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.precamres.2007.04.013>
- Anand, R., Paul, L., & Chanway, C. (2007). Research on Endophytic Bacteria: Recent Advances with Forest Trees. *Microbial Root Endophytes*, *9*, 89–106. https://doi.org/10.1007/3-540-33526-9_6
- Andersson, M. N., Grosse-Wilde, E., Keeling, C. I., Bengtsson, J. M., Yuen, M. M. S., Li, M., Hillbur, Y., Bohlmann, J., Hansson, B. S., & Schlyter, F. (2013). Antennal transcriptome analysis of the chemosensory gene families in the tree killing bark beetles, *Ips typographus* and *Dendroctonus ponderosae* (Coleoptera: Curculionidae: Scolytinae). *BMC Genomics*, *14*(1).
<https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2164-14-198>
- Appel, H. M., & Maines, L. W. (1995). The influence of host plant on gut conditions of gypsy moth (*Lymantria dispar*) caterpillars. *Journal of Insect Physiology*, *41*(3), 241–246.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-1910\(94\)00106-Q](https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-1910(94)00106-Q)

- Arntzen, M., Bengtsson, O., Várnai, A., Delogu, F., Mathiesen, G., & Eijsink, V. G. H. (2020). Quantitative comparison of the biomass-degrading enzyme repertoires of five filamentous fungi. *Scientific Reports*, *10*(1), 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-75217-z>
- Arora, A. K., & Douglas, A. E. (2017). Hype or opportunity? Using microbial symbionts in novel strategies for insect pest control. *Journal of Insect Physiology*, *103*, 10–17. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jinsphys.2017.09.011>
- Augustine, S. K., Bhavsar, S. P., & Kapadnis, B. P. (2005). A non-polyene antifungal antibiotic from *Streptomyces albidoflavus* PU 23. *Journal of Biosciences*, *30*(2), 201–211. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02703700>
- Ayres, M. P., Wilkens, R. T., Ruel, J. J., Lombardero, M. J., & Vallery, E. (2000). Nitrogen Budgets of Phloem-Feeding Bark Beetles with and without Symbiotic Fungi. *Ecology*, *81*(8), 2198. <https://doi.org/10.2307/177108>
- Bang-Andreasen, T., Anwar, M. ʘ., Lanzén, A., Kjøller, R., Rønn, R., Ekelund, F., & Jacobsen, C. S. (2019). Total RNA sequencing reveals multilevel microbial community changes and functional responses to wood ash application in agricultural and forest soil. *FEMS Microbiology Ecology*, *96*(3), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1093/femsec/fiaa016>
- Baños-Quintana, A. P., Gershenson, J., & Kaltenpoth, M. (2024). The Eurasian spruce bark beetle *Ips typographus* shapes the microbial communities of its offspring and the gallery environment. *Frontiers in Microbiology*, *15*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2024.1367127>
- Banskar, S., Mourya, D. T., & Shouche, Y. S. (2016). Bacterial diversity indicates dietary overlap among bats of different feeding habits. *Microbiological Research*, *182*, 99–108. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.micres.2015.10.006>
- Barcoto, M. O., Carlos-Shanley, C., Fan, H., Ferro, M., Nagamoto, N. S., Bacci, M., Currie, C. R., & Rodrigues, A. (2020). Fungus-growing insects host a distinctive microbiota apparently adapted to the fungiculture environment. *Scientific Reports*, *10*(1), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-68448-7>
- Baumann, P. (2005). Biology of bacteriocyte-associated endosymbionts of plant sap-sucking insects. *Annual Review of Microbiology*, *59*, 155–189. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.micro.59.030804.121041>
- Bentz, B. J., Jönsson, A. M., Schroeder, M., Weed, A., Wilcke, R. A. I., & Larsson, K. (2019). *Ips typographus* and *Dendroctonus ponderosae* Models Project Thermal Suitability for Intra- and Inter-Continental Establishment in a Changing Climate. *Frontiers in Forests and Global Change*, *2*(March). <https://doi.org/10.3389/ffgc.2019.00001>
- Bentz, B. J., Rgnire, J., Fettig, C. J., Hansen, E. M., Hayes, J. L., Hicke, J. A., Kelsey, R. G., Negron, J. F., & Seybold, S. J. (2010). Climate change and bark beetles of the western United States and Canada: Direct and indirect effects. *BioScience*, *60*(8), 602–613. <https://doi.org/10.1525/bio.2010.60.8.6>
- Bentz, B., Logan, J., MacMahon, J., Allen, C. D., Ayres, M., Berg, E., Carroll, A., Hansen, M., Hicke, J., Joyce, L., Macfarlane, W., Munson, S., Negron, J., Paine, T., Powell, J., Raffa, K., Regniere, J., Reid, M., Romme, B., ... Wood, D. (2009). Bark beetle outbreaks in western North America: Causes and consequences. *Bark Beetle Symposium, November*, 42. https://www.fs.fed.us/rm/pubs_other/rmrs_2009_bentz_b001.pdf

- Biedermann, P. H. W., Müller, J., Grégoire, J. C., Gruppe, A., Hagge, J., Hammerbacher, A., Hofstetter, R. W., Kandasamy, D., Kolarik, M., Kostovcik, M., Krokene, P., Sallé, A., Six, D. L., Turrini, T., Vanderpool, D., Wingfield, M. J., & Bässler, C. (2019a). Bark Beetle Population Dynamics in the Anthropocene: Challenges and Solutions. *Trends in Ecology and Evolution*, *34*(10), 914–924. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2019.06.002>
- Biedermann, P. H. W., Müller, J., Grégoire, J. C., Gruppe, A., Hagge, J., Hammerbacher, A., Hofstetter, R. W., Kandasamy, D., Kolarik, M., Kostovcik, M., Krokene, P., Sallé, A., Six, D. L., Turrini, T., Vanderpool, D., Wingfield, M. J., & Bässler, C. (2019b). Bark Beetle Population Dynamics in the Anthropocene: Challenges and Solutions. *Trends in Ecology and Evolution*, *34*(10), 914–924. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2019.06.002>
- Biedermann, P. H. W., Müller, J., Grégoire, J. C., Gruppe, A., Hagge, J., Hammerbacher, A., Hofstetter, R. W., Kandasamy, D., Kolarik, M., Kostovcik, M., Krokene, P., Sallé, A., Six, D. L., Turrini, T., Vanderpool, D., Wingfield, M. J., & Bässler, C. (2019c). Bark Beetle Population Dynamics in the Anthropocene: Challenges and Solutions. *Trends in Ecology and Evolution*, *34*(10), 914–924. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2019.06.002>
- Biedermann, P. H. W., & Vega, F. E. (2020). Annual Review of Entomology Ecology and Evolution of Insect – Fungus Mutualisms. *Annual Review of Entomology*, *65*, 431–455.
- Boone, C. K., Keefover-Ring, K., Mapes, A. C., Adams, A. S., Bohlmann, J., & Raffa, K. F. (2013). Bacteria Associated with a Tree-Killing Insect Reduce Concentrations of Plant Defense Compounds. *Journal of Chemical Ecology*, *39*(7), 1003–1006. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10886-013-0313-0>
- Boucher, D. (2016). Mutualism. *Integrative and Comparative Biology*, *56*(2), 365–367. <https://doi.org/10.1093/icb/icw071>
- Bracewell, R. R., & Six, D. L. (2015). Experimental evidence of bark beetle adaptation to a fungal symbiont. *Ecology and Evolution*, *5*(21), 5109–5119. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ece3.1772>
- Bright, M., & Bulgheresi, S. (2010). A complex journey: Transmission of microbial symbionts. *Nature Reviews Microbiology*, *8*(3), 218–230. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrmicro2262>
- Briones-Roblero, C. I., Hernández-García, J. A., Gonzalez-Escobedo, R., Soto-Robles, L. V., Rivera-Orduña, F. N., & Úñiga, G. (2017). Structure and dynamics of the gut bacterial microbiota of the bark beetle, *Dendroctonus rhizophagus* (Curculionidae: Scolytinae) across their life stages. *PLoS ONE*, *12*(4), 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0175470>
- Calevro, F., Callaerts, P., Matsuura, Y., & Michalik, A. (2023). Editorial: Symbiotic organs in insects: development, metabolism, and physiological regulation. *Frontiers in Physiology*, *14*(July), 5–7. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphys.2023.1248654>
- Carter, D. O., Metcalf, J. L., Bibat, A., & Knight, R. (2015). Seasonal variation of postmortem microbial communities. *Forensic Science, Medicine, and Pathology*, *11*(2), 202–207. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12024-015-9667-7>
- Cavanaugh, C. M., McKiness, P., Newton, I. L. G., & Stewart, F. J. (2013). Marine chemosynthetic symbioses. In *The Prokaryotes: Prokaryotic Biology and Symbiotic Associations* (Issue December). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-30194-0_21

- Chakraborty, A., Ashraf, M. , Modlinger, R., Synek, J., Schlyter, F., & Roy, A. (2020). Unravelling the gut bacteriome of Ips (Coleoptera: Curculionidae: Scolytinae): identifying core bacterial assemblage and their ecological relevance. *Scientific Reports*, *10*(1), 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-75203-5>
- Chakraborty, A., Modlinger, R., Ashraf, M. , Synek, J., Schlyter, F., & Roy, A. (2020a). Core Mycobiome and Their Ecological Relevance in the Gut of Five Ips Bark Beetles (Coleoptera: Curculionidae: Scolytinae). *Frontiers in Microbiology*, *11*(September), 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2020.568853>
- Chakraborty, A., Modlinger, R., Ashraf, M. , Synek, J., Schlyter, F., & Roy, A. (2020b). Core Mycobiome and Their Ecological Relevance in the Gut of Five Ips Bark Beetles (Coleoptera: Curculionidae: Scolytinae). *Frontiers in Microbiology*, *11*(September). <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2020.568853>
- Chakraborty, A., Purohit, A., Khara, A., Modlinger, R., & Roy, A. (2023). Life-stage and geographic location determine the microbial assemblage in Eurasian spruce bark beetle, Ips typographus L. (Coleoptera: Curculionidae). *Frontiers in Forests and Global Change*, *6*(July). <https://doi.org/10.3389/ffgc.2023.1176160>
- Chen, X., Hitchings, M. D., Mendoza, J. E., Balanza, V., Facey, P. D., Dyson, P. J., Bielza, P., & Del Sol, R. (2017). Comparative genomics of facultative bacterial symbionts isolated from European Orius species reveals an ancestral symbiotic association. *Frontiers in Microbiology*, *8*(OCT), 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2017.01969>
- Cheng, T., Veselská, T., Křížková, B., Švec, K., Havlíček, V., Stadler, M., & Kolařík, M. (2023). Insight into the genomes of dominant yeast symbionts of European spruce bark beetle, Ips typographus. *Frontiers in Microbiology*, *14*(April), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2023.1108975>
- Chettri, D., Verma, A. K., & Verma, A. K. (2020). Innovations in CAZyme gene diversity and its modification for biorefinery applications. *Biotechnology Reports*, *28*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.btre.2020.e00525>
- Claesson, M. J., Wang, Q., O’Sullivan, O., Greene-Diniz, R., Cole, J. R., Ross, R. P., & O’Toole, P. W. (2010). Comparison of two next-generation sequencing technologies for resolving highly complex microbiota composition using tandem variable 16S rRNA gene regions. *Nucleic Acids Research*, *38*(22). <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkq873>
- Comeau, A. M., Dufour, J., Bouvet, G. F., Jacobi, V., Nigg, M., Henrissat, B., Laroche, J., Levesque, R. C., & Bernier, L. (2015). Functional annotation of the ophiostoma novo-ulmi genome: Insights into the phytopathogenicity of the fungal agent of Dutch elm disease. *Genome Biology and Evolution*, *7*(2), 410–430. <https://doi.org/10.1093/gbe/evu281>
- Davis, T. S., Rhoades, P. R., Mann, A. J., & Griswold, T. (2020). Bark beetle outbreak enhances biodiversity and foraging habitat of native bees in alpine landscapes of the southern Rocky Mountains. *Scientific Reports*, *10*(1), 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-73273-z>
- DiGuistini, S., Wang, Y., Liao, N. Y., Taylor, G., Tanguay, P., Feau, N., Henrissat, B., Chan, S. K., Hesse-Orce, U., Alamouti, S. M., Tsui, C. K. M., Docking, R. T., Levasseur, A., Haridas, S., Robertson, G., Birol, I., Holt, R. A., Marra, M. A., Hamelin, R. C., ... Breuil, C. (2011). Genome and transcriptome analyses of the mountain pine beetle-fungal symbiont

- Grosmannia clavigera, a lodgepole pine pathogen. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 108(6), 2504–2509.
<https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1011289108>
- Douglas, A. E. (2014). *Evolution*. 1–13.
- Douglas, A. E. (2021). The symbiotic habit. In *The Symbiotic Habit*.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1442-9993.2011.02287.x>
- El-Goorani, M. A., Hassanein, F. M., & Shoeib, A. A. (1992). Antibacterial and Antifungal Spectra of Antibiotics Produced by Different Strains of *Erwinia herbicola* (= *Pantoea agglomerans*). *Journal of Phytopathology*, 136(4), 335–339. [file:///C:/Users/svecka/OneDrive-MBU_AVCR. https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1439-0434.1992.tb01316.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1439-0434.1992.tb01316.x)
- Engel, P., & Moran, N. A. (2013). The gut microbiota of insects - diversity in structure and function. *FEMS Microbiology Reviews*, 37(5), 699–735. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1574-6976.12025>
- Erler, F., & Ates, A. O. (2015). Potential of two entomopathogenic fungi, *beauveria bassiana* and *metarhizium anisopliae* (Coleoptera: Scarabaeidae), as biological control agents against the june beetle. *Journal of Insect Science*, 15(1), 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jisesa/iev029>
- Fabryová, A., Kostovčík, M., Díez-Méndez, A., Jiménez-Gómez, A., Celador-Lera, L., Saati-Santamaría, M., Sechovcová, H., Menéndez, E., Kolařík, M., & García-Fraile, P. (2018). On the bright side of a forest pest-the metabolic potential of bark beetles' bacterial associates. *Science of the Total Environment*, 619–620, 9–17.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2017.11.074>
- Fang, J. X., Zhang, S. F., Liu, F., Zhang, X., Zhang, F. Bin, Guo, X. Bin, Zhang, M., Zhang, Q. H., & Kong, X. B. (2020). Differences in gut bacterial communities of *ips typographus* (Coleoptera: Curculionidae) induced by enantiomer-specific α -pinene. *Environmental Entomology*, 49(5), 1198–1205. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ee/nvaa098>
- Ferrari, J., & Vavre, F. (2011). Bacterial symbionts in insects or the story of communities affecting communities. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 366(1569), 1389–1400. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2010.0226>
- Fettig, C. J., Asaro, C., Nowak, J. T., Dodds, K. J., Gandhi, K. J. K., Moan, J. E., & Robert, J. (2022). Trends in Bark Beetle Impacts in North America During a Period (2000–2020) of Rapid Environmental Change. *Journal of Forestry*, 120(6), 693–713.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/jofore/fvac021>
- Gandhi, K. J. K., & Hofstetter, R. W. (2021). Bark Beetle Management, Ecology, and Climate Change. In *Bark Beetle Management, Ecology, and Climate Change*.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/C2019-0-04282-3>
- García-Fraile, P. (2018). Roles of bacteria in the bark beetle holobiont – how do they shape this forest pest? *Annals of Applied Biology*, 172(2), 111–125. <https://doi.org/10.1111/aab.12406>
- Gibson, C. M., & Hunter, M. S. (2010). Extraordinarily widespread and fantastically complex: Comparative biology of endosymbiotic bacterial and fungal mutualists of insects. *Ecology Letters*, 13(2), 223–234. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1461-0248.2009.01416.x>

- Gilbert, S. F., Sapp, J., & Tauber, A. I. (2012). A symbiotic view of life: We have never been individuals. *Quarterly Review of Biology*, 87(4), 325–341. <https://doi.org/10.1086/668166>
- Giordano, L., Garbelotto, M., Nicolotti, G., & Gonthier, P. (2013). Characterization of fungal communities associated with the bark beetle *Ips typographus* varies depending on detection method, location, and beetle population levels. *Mycological Progress*, 12(1), 127–140. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11557-012-0822-1>
- González-Serrano, F., Pérez-Cobas, A. E., Rosas, T., Baixeras, J., Latorre, A., & Moya, A. (2020). The Gut Microbiota Composition of the Moth *Brithys crini* Reflects Insect Metamorphosis. *Microbial Ecology*, 79(4), 960–970. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00248-019-01460-1>
- Hagen, B. W. (2002). Managing Bark Beetles in Urban and Rural Trees. In *Tree notes 19*. <http://ceres.ca.gov/foreststeward/pdf/treenote19.pdf>
- Hammer, T. J., Sanders, J. G., & Fierer, N. (2019). Not all animals need a microbiome. *FEMS Microbiology Letters*, 366(10). <https://doi.org/10.1093/femsle/fnz117>
- Hammerbacher, A., Schmidt, A., Wadke, N., Wright, L. P., Schneider, B., Bohlmann, J., Brand, W. A., Fenning, T. M., Gershenzon, J., & Paetz, C. (2013). A common fungal associate of the spruce bark beetle metabolizes the stilbene defenses of Norway spruce. *Plant Physiology*, 162(3), 1324–1336. <https://doi.org/10.1104/pp.113.218610>
- Hernández-García, J. A., Gonzalez-Escobedo, R., Briones-Roblero, C. I., Cano-Ramírez, C., Rivera-Orduña, F. N., & Úñiga, G. (2018). Gut bacterial communities of *dendroctonus valens* and *D. Mexicanus* (curculionidae: Scolytinae): A metagenomic analysis across different geographical locations in Mexico. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 19(9). <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms19092578>
- Hlásny, T., König, L., Krokene, P., Lindner, M., Montagné-Huck, C., Müller, J., Qin, H., Raffa, K. F., Schelhaas, M. J., Svoboda, M., Viiri, H., & Seidl, R. (2021a). Bark Beetle Outbreaks in Europe: State of Knowledge and Ways Forward for Management. *Current Forestry Reports*, 7(3), 138–165. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40725-021-00142-x>
- Hlásny, T., König, L., Krokene, P., Lindner, M., Montagné-Huck, C., Müller, J., Qin, H., Raffa, K. F., Schelhaas, M. J., Svoboda, M., Viiri, H., & Seidl, R. (2021b). Bark Beetle Outbreaks in Europe: State of Knowledge and Ways Forward for Management. *Current Forestry Reports*, 7(3), 138–165. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40725-021-00142-x>
- Hlásny, T., Krokene, P., Liebhold, A., Montagné-Huck, C., Müller, J., Qin, H., Raffa, K., Schelhaas, M.-J., Seidl, R., Svoboda, M., & Viiri, H. (2019). Living with bark beetles: impacts , outlook and management options. In *From Science to Policy* (Vol. 8, Issue April).
- Hofstetter, R. W., Dinkins-Bookwalter, J., Davis, T. S., & Klepzig, K. D. (2015). Symbiotic Associations of Bark Beetles. *Bark Beetles: Biology and Ecology of Native and Invasive Species*, January, 209–245. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-417156-5.00006-X>
- Hosokawa, T., & Fukatsu, T. (2020). Relevance of microbial symbiosis to insect behavior. *Current Opinion in Insect Science*, 39, 91–100. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cois.2020.03.004>
- Hulcr, J., & Stelinski, L. L. (2017). The Ambrosia Symbiosis: From Evolutionary Ecology to Practical Management. *Annual Review of Entomology*, 62, 285–303. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-ento-031616-035105>

- Ibarra-Juarez, L., Burton, MA., Biedermann, P., Cruz, L., Desgarenes, D., Ibarra-Laclette, E., Latorre, A., Alonso-Sánchez, A., Villafan, E., Hanako-Rosas, G., López, L., Vázquez-Rosas-Landa, M., Carrion, G., Carrillo, D., Moya, A., & Lamelas, A. (2020). *Microbial symbionts in ambrosia beetles: Putative roles and dynamics during its host's life cycle*. 1–53.
- Jaime, L., Batllori, E., & Lloret, F. (2023). Bark beetle outbreaks in coniferous forests: a review of climate change effects. *European Journal of Forest Research*, *143*(1), 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10342-023-01623-3>
- Jankowiak, B. R. (2005). *Fungi associated with Ips typographus on Picea abies in southern Poland and their succession into the phloem and sapwood of beetle-infested trees and logs*. *35*, 37–55.
- Jankowiak, R. (2005). Fungi associated with Ips typographus on Picea abies in southern Poland and their succession into the phloem and sapwood of beetle-infested trees and logs. *Forest Pathology*, *35*(1), 37–55. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1439-0329.2004.00395.x>
- Jankowiak, R., & Bilański, P. (2018). Geosmithia species associated with fir-infesting beetles in Poland. *Acta Mycologica*, *53*(2), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.5586/am.1115>
- Jankowiak, R., & Hilszczański, J. (2005). Ophiostomatoid fungi associated with Ips typographus (L.) on Picea abies [(L.) H. Karst.] and Pinus sylvestris L. in north-eastern Poland. *Acta Societatis Botanicorum Poloniae*, *74*(4), 345–350. <https://doi.org/10.5586/asbp.2005.043>
- Jankowiak, R., Kacprzyk, M., & Młynarczyk, M. (2009). Diversity of ophiostomatoid fungi associated with bark beetles (Coleoptera: Scolytidae) colonizing branches of Norway spruce (Picea abies) in southern Poland. *Biologia*, *64*(6), 1170–1177. <https://doi.org/10.2478/s11756-009-0188-2>
- Jones, A. G., Mason, C. J., Felton, G. W., & Hoover, K. (2019). Host plant and population source drive diversity of microbial gut communities in two polyphagous insects. *Scientific Reports*, *9*(1), 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-019-39163-9>
- Karpov, A., Pirtskhalava-Karpova, N., Trubin, A., Mezei, P., Potterf, M., & Jakuš, R. (2024). Infestation patterns of two bark beetle species in multi-species coniferous forests on Kunashir Island in North Pacific Ocean region. *Forest Ecology and Management*, *558*(June 2023). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foreco.2024.121774>
- Khara, A., Chakraborty, A., Modlinger, R., Synek, J., & Roy, A. (2024). Comparative metagenomic study unveils new insights on bacterial communities in two pine-feeding Ips beetles (Coleoptera: Curculionidae: Scolytinae). *Frontiers in Microbiology*, *15*(October), 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2024.1400894>
- Kikuchi, Y., Hosokawa, T., & Fukatsu, T. (2007). Insect-microbe mutualism without vertical transmission: A stinkbug acquires a beneficial gut symbiont from the environment every generation. *Applied and Environmental Microbiology*, *73*(13), 4308–4316. <https://doi.org/10.1128/AEM.00067-07>
- Kirisits, T. (2004). Fungal associates of European bark beetles with special emphasis on the ophiostomatoid fungi. *Bark and Wood Boring Insects in Living Trees in Europe.*, 181–235. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13398-014-0173-7.2>

- Kirkendall, L. R., Biedermann, P. H. W., & Jordal, B. H. (2015). Evolution and Diversity of Bark and Ambrosia Beetles. In *Bark Beetles: Biology and Ecology of Native and Invasive Species* (Issue May 2018). <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-417156-5.00003-4>
- Kjærboelling, I., Vesth, T., Frisvad, J. C., Nybo, J. L., Theobald, S., Kildgaard, S., Petersen, T. I., Kuo, A., Sato, A., Lyhne, E. K., Kogle, M. E., Wiebenga, A., Kun, R. S., Lubbers, R. J. M., Mäkelä, M. R., Barry, K., Chovatia, M., Clum, A., Daum, C., ... Andersen, M. R. (2020). A comparative genomics study of 23 *Aspergillus* species from section *Flavi*. *Nature Communications*, *11*(1). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-019-14051-y>
- Klepzig, K. D., & Six, D. L. (2004). Bark beetle-fungal symbiosis: Context dependency in complex associations. *Symbiosis*, *37*(1–3), 189–205.
- Kolařík, M., & Hulcr, J. (2023). *Geosmithia*—widespread and abundant but long ignored bark beetle symbionts. In *Mycological Progress* (Vol. 22, Issue 4). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11557-023-01880-x>
- Kulakowski, D. (2016). Managing bark beetle outbreaks (*Ips typographus*, *Dendroctonus* spp.) in conservation areas in the 21st century. *Forest Research Papers*, *77*(4), 352–357. <https://doi.org/10.1515/frp-2016-0036>
- Lehenberger, M., Foh, N., Göttlein, A., Six, D., & Biedermann, P. H. W. (2021). Nutrient-Poor Breeding Substrates of Ambrosia Beetles Are Enriched With Biologically Important Elements. *Frontiers in Microbiology*, *12*(April), 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2021.664542>
- Li, Y., Bateman, C., Skelton, J., Wang, B., Black, A., Huang, Y. T., Gonzalez, A., Jusino, M. A., Nolen, J., Freeman, S., Mendel, J., Kolarik, M., Knizek, M., Park, J. H., Sittichaya, W., Pham, T. H., Ito, S. I., Torii, M., Gao, L., ... Hulcr, J. (2022). Preinvasion Assessment of Exotic Bark Beetle-Vectored Fungi to Detect Tree-Killing Pathogens. *Phytopathology*, *112*(2), 261–270. <https://doi.org/10.1094/PHYTO-01-21-0041-R>
- Linder, T. (2019). Taxonomic distribution of cytochrome p450 monooxygenases (Cyps) among the budding yeasts (sub-phylum saccharomycotina). *Microorganisms*, *7*(8). <https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms7080247>
- Linnakoski, R., Lasarov, I., Veteli, P., Tikkanen, O. P., Viiri, H., Jyske, T., Kasanen, R., Duong, T. A., & Wingfield, M. J. (2021). Filamentous fungi and yeasts associated with mites phoretic on *ips typographus* in Eastern Finland. *Forests*, *12*(6), 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.3390/f12060743>
- Linnakoski, R., Mahilainen, S., Harrington, A., Vanhanen, H., Eriksson, M., Mehtatalo, L., Pappinen, A., & Wingfield, M. J. (2016). Seasonal succession of fungi associated with *ips typographus* beetles and their Phoretic mites in an outbreak region of Finland. *PLoS ONE*, *11*(5). <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0155622>
- Linnakoski, R., Sugano, J., Junttila, S., Pulkkinen, P., Asiegbu, F. O., & Forbes, K. M. (2017). Effects of water availability on a forestry pathosystem: fungal strain-specific variation in disease severity. *Scientific Reports*, *7*(1), 13501. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-017-13512-y>
- Linnakoski, R., Wilhelm de Beer, B., Niemelä, P., & Wingfield, M. J. (2012). Associations of conifer-infesting bark beetles and fungi in Fennoscandia. *Insects*, *3*(1), 200–227. <https://doi.org/10.3390/insects3010200>

- Liu, C. H., Chen, X., Liu, T. T., Lian, B., Gu, Y., Caer, V., Xue, Y. R., & Wang, B. T. (2007). Study of the antifungal activity of *Acinetobacter baumannii* LCH001 in vitro and identification of its antifungal components. *Applied Microbiology and Biotechnology*, *76*(2), 459–466. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00253-007-1010-0>
- Lou, Q. 2., Lu, M., & Sun, J. H. (2014). Yeast Diversity Associated with Invasive *Dendroctonus valens* Killing *Pinus tabulaeformis* in China Using Culturing and Molecular Methods. *Microbial Ecology*, *68*(2), 397–415. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00248-014-0413-6>
- Louca, S., Jacques, S. M. S., Pires, A. P. F., Leal, J. S., Srivastava, D. S., Parfrey, L. W., Farjalla, V. F., & Doebeli, M. (2017). High taxonomic variability despite stable functional structure across microbial communities. *Nature Ecology & Evolution*, *1*(1), 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-016-0015>
- Lu, M., Hulcr, J., & Sun, J. (2016). The Role of Symbiotic Microbes in Insect Invasions. *Annual Review of Ecology, Evolution, and Systematics*, *47*, 487–505. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-ecolsys-121415-032050>
- Lundquist, J. E. (2019). Impacts of bark beetles on ecosystem values in western forests—introduction. *Journal of Forestry*, *117*(2), 136–137. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jofore/fvy075>
- Mezei, P., Blaženec, M., Grodzki, W., Škvarenina, J., & Jakuš, R. (2017). Influence of different forest protection strategies on spruce tree mortality during a bark beetle outbreak. *Annals of Forest Science*, *74*(4). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13595-017-0663-9>
- Mindell, D. P. (1992). Phylogenetic consequences of symbioses: Eukarya and Eubacteria are not monophyletic taxa. *BioSystems*, *27*(1), 53–62. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0303-2647\(92\)90046-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/0303-2647(92)90046-2)
- Mondal, S., Somani, J., Roy, S., Babu, A., & Pandey, A. K. (2023). Insect Microbial Symbionts: Ecology, Interactions, and Biological Significance. *Microorganisms*, *11*(11). <https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms11112665>
- Monnin, D., Jackson, R., Kiers, E. T., Bunker, M., Ellers, J., & Henry, L. M. (2020). Parallel Evolution in the Integration of a Co-obligate Aphid Symbiosis. *Current Biology*, *30*(10), 1949–1957.e6. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cub.2020.03.011>
- Morales-Jiménez, J., 2úñiga, G., Ramírez-Saad, H. C., & Hernández-Rodríguez, C. (2012a). Gut-Associated Bacteria Throughout the Life Cycle of the Bark Beetle *Dendroctonus rhizophagus* Thomas and Bright (Curculionidae: Scolytinae) and Their Cellulolytic Activities. *Microbial Ecology*, *64*(1), 268–278. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00248-011-9999-0>
- Morales-Jiménez, J., 2úñiga, G., Ramírez-Saad, H. C., & Hernández-Rodríguez, C. (2012b). Gut-Associated Bacteria Throughout the Life Cycle of the Bark Beetle *Dendroctonus rhizophagus* Thomas and Bright (Curculionidae: Scolytinae) and Their Cellulolytic Activities. *Microbial Ecology*, *64*(1), 268–278. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00248-011-9999-0>
- Morales-Jiménez, J., 2úñiga, G., Villa-Tanaca, L., & Hernández-Rodríguez, C. (2009). Bacterial community and nitrogen fixation in the red turpentine beetle, *dendroctonus valens* LeConte (Coleoptera: Curculionidae: Scolytinae). *Microbial Ecology*, *58*(4), 879–891. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00248-009-9548-2>

- Moran, N. A. (2006). Symbiosis. *Current Biology*, 16(20), 866–871.
<https://doi.org/doi:10.1016/j.cub.2006.09.019>
- Moran, N. A. (2007). Symbiosis as an adaptive process and source of phenotypic complexity. *In the Light of Evolution*, 1, 165–181. <https://doi.org/10.17226/11790>
- Moran, N. A., Degnan, P. H., Santos, S. R., Dunbar, H. E., & Ochman, H. (2005). The players in a mutualistic symbiosis: Insects, bacteria, viruses, and virulence genes. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 102(47), 16919–16926.
<https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0507029102>
- Moran, N. A., & Telang, A. (1998). Bacteriocyte-Associated symbiotic of insects: A variety of insect groups harbor ancient prokaryotic endosymbionts. *BioScience*, 48(4), 295–304.
<https://doi.org/10.2307/1313356>
- Moran, N. A., & Yun, Y. (2015). Experimental replacement of an obligate insect symbiont. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 112(7), 2093–2096. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1420037112>
- Moussa, A., Nones, S., Vannucchi, P. E., Shahzad, G. I. R., Dittmer, J., Corretto, E., Schebeck, M., Faccoli, M., Battisti, A., Stauffer, C., & Schuler, H. (2024). The bacterial community of the European spruce bark beetle in space and time. *Entomologia Generalis*, 44(1), 211–222.
<https://doi.org/10.1127/entomologia/2023/2114>
- Muthukrishnan, S., Mun, S., Noh, M. Y., Geisbrecht, E. R., & Arakane, Y. (2020). Insect Cuticular Chitin Contributes to Form and Function. In *Current Pharmaceutical Design* (Vol. 26, Issue 29). <https://doi.org/10.2174/1381612826666200523175409>
- Nagpure, A., Choudhary, B., Kumar, S., & Gupta, R. K. (2014). Isolation and characterization of chitinolytic *Streptomyces* sp. MT7 and its antagonism towards wood-rotting fungi. *Annals of Microbiology*, 64(2), 531–541. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13213-013-0686-x>
- Naseer, A., Mogilicherla, K., Sellamuthu, G., & Roy, A. (2023). Age matters: Life-stage, tissue, and sex-specific gene expression dynamics in *Ips typographus* (Coleoptera: Curculionidae: Scolytinae). *Frontiers in Forests and Global Change*, 6(March).
<https://doi.org/10.3389/ffgc.2023.1124754>
- Netherer, S., Kandasamy, D., Jirosová, A., Kalinová, B., Schebeck, M., & Schlyter, F. (2021). Interactions among Norway spruce, the bark beetle *Ips typographus* and its fungal symbionts in times of drought. *Journal of Pest Science*, 94(3), 591–614.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10340-021-01341-y>
- Paine, T. D., Raffa, K. F., & Harrington, T. C. (1997). Interactions among scolytid bark beetles, their associated fungi, and live host conifers. *Annual Review of Entomology*, 42(April 2014), 179–206. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.ento.42.1.179>
- Pažoutová, S., Šrůtka, P., Holuša, J., Chudíčková, M., & Kolařík, M. (2010). Diversity of xylariaceous symbionts in Xiphydria woodwasps: Role of vector and a host tree. *Fungal Ecology*, 3(4), 392–401. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.funeco.2010.07.002>
- Peral-aranega, E. (2020). *nov . from the Bark Beetle Ips typographus Have.*
- Peral-Aranega, E., Saati-Santamaría, J., Ayuso-Calles, M., Kostovčík, M., Veselská, T., Švec, K., Rivas, R., Kolařík, M., & García-Fraile, P. (2023). New insight into the bark beetle ips

- typographus bacteriome reveals unexplored diversity potentially beneficial to the host. *Environmental Microbiome*, 18(1), 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40793-023-00510-z>
- Peral-Aranega, E., Saati-Santamaría, , Kolařík, M., Rivas, R., & García-Fraile, P. (2020). Bacteria belonging to *Pseudomonas typographi* sp. nov. from the bark beetle *Ips typographus* have genomic potential to aid in the host ecology. *Insects*, 11(9), 1–22. <https://doi.org/10.3390/insects11090593>
- Powell, D., Große-Wilde, E., Krokene, P., Roy, A., Chakraborty, A., Löfstedt, C., Vogel, H., Andersson, M. N., & Schlyter, F. (2021). A highly-contiguous genome assembly of the Eurasian spruce bark beetle, *Ips typographus*, provides insight into a major forest pest. *Communications Biology*, 4(1), 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s42003-021-02602-3>
- Prapagdee, B., Kuekulvong, C., & Mongkolsuk, S. (2008). Antifungal potential of extracellular metabolites produced by *Streptomyces hygrosopicus* against phytopathogenic fungi. *International Journal of Biological Sciences*, 4(5), 330–337. <https://doi.org/10.7150/ijbs.4.330>
- Raaska, L., & Mattila-Sandholm, T. (1995). Effects of iron level on the antagonistic action of siderophores from non-pathogenic *Staphylococcus* spp. *Journal of Industrial Microbiology*, 15(6), 480–485. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01570018>
- Ramakrishnan, R., Hradecký, J., Roy, A., Kalinová, B., Mendezes, R. C., Synek, J., Bláha, J., Svatoš, A., & Jirošová, A. (2022). Metabolomics and transcriptomics of pheromone biosynthesis in an aggressive forest pest *Ips typographus*. *Insect Biochemistry and Molecular Biology*, 140(August 2021). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ibmb.2021.103680>
- Repe, A., Kirisits, T., Piškur, B., De Groot, M., Kump, B., & Jurc, M. (2013a). Ophiostomatoid fungi associated with three spruce-infesting bark beetles in Slovenia. *Annals of Forest Science*, 70(7), 717–727. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13595-013-0311-y>
- Repe, A., Kirisits, T., Piškur, B., De Groot, M., Kump, B., & Jurc, M. (2013b). Ophiostomatoid fungi associated with three spruce-infesting bark beetles in Slovenia. *Annals of Forest Science*, 70(7), 717–727. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13595-013-0311-y>
- Risely, A. (2020). Applying the core microbiome to understand host–microbe systems. *Journal of Animal Ecology*, 89(7), 1549–1558. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2656.13229>
- Rodman, K. C., Andrus, R. A., Butkiewicz, C. L., Chapman, T. B., Gill, N. S., Harvey, B. J., Kulakowski, D., Tutland, N. J., Veblen, T. T., & Hart, S. J. (2021). Effects of bark beetle outbreaks on forest landscape pattern in the southern rocky mountains, U.S.A. *Remote Sensing*, 13(6), 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs13061089>
- Saati-Santamaría, , López-Mondéjar, R., Jiménez-Gómez, A., Díez-Méndez, A., Vetrovský, T., Igual, J. M., Velázquez, E., Kolarik, M., Rivas, R., & García-Fraile, P. (2018). Discovery of phloeophagus beetles as a source of *Pseudomonas* strains that produce potentially new bioactive substances and description of *Pseudomonas bohémica* sp. nov. *Frontiers in Microbiology*, 9(MAY). <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2018.00913>
- Saati-Santamaría, , Rivas, R., Kolařík, M., & García-Fraile, P. (2021). A new perspective of *Pseudomonas*-host interactions: Distribution and potential ecological functions of the genus *Pseudomonas* within the bark beetle holobiont. *Biology*, 10(2), 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.3390/biology10020164>

- Schopf, J. W., Kitajima, K., Spicuzza, M. J., Kudryavtsev, A. B., & Valley, J. W. (2018). SIMS analyses of the oldest known assemblage of microfossils document their taxon-correlated carbon isotope compositions. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, *115*(1), 53–58. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1718063115>
- Schuelke, T. A., Wu, G., Westbrook, A., Woeste, K., Plachetzki, D. C., Broders, K., & Macmanes, M. D. (2017). Comparative Genomics of Pathogenic and Nonpathogenic Beetle-Vectored Fungi in the Genus *Geosmithia*. *Genome Biology and Evolution*, *9*(12), 3312–3327. <https://doi.org/10.1093/gbe/evx242>
- Schultz, T. R., & Brady, S. G. (2008). Major evolutionary transitions in ant agriculture. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, *105*(14), 5435–5440. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0711024105>
- Seidl, R., Thom, D., Kautz, M., Martin-Benito, D., Peltoniemi, M., Vacchiano, G., Wild, J., Ascoli, D., Petr, M., Honkaniemi, J., Lexer, M. J., Trotsiuk, V., Mairota, P., Svoboda, M., Fabrika, M., Nagel, T. A., & Reyer, C. P. O. (2017). Forest disturbances under climate change. *Nature Climate Change*, *7*(6), 395–402. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nclimate3303>
- Shamjana, U., Vasu, D. A., Hembrom, P. S., Nayak, K., & Grace, T. (2024). The role of insect gut microbiota in host fitness, detoxification and nutrient supplementation. *Antonie van Leeuwenhoek, International Journal of General and Molecular Microbiology*, *117*(1), 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10482-024-01970-0>
- Šigut, M., Pyszko, P., Šigutová, H., Višňovská, D., Kostovčík, M., Kotásková, N., Dorňák, O., Kolařík, M., & Drozd, P. (2022). Fungi are more transient than bacteria in caterpillar gut microbiomes. *Scientific Reports*, *12*(1), 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-19855-5>
- Six, D. L. (2013). *The Bark Beetle Holobiont : Why Microbes Matter*. 989–1002. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10886-013-0318-8>
- Six, D. L. (2020). A major symbiont shift supports a major niche shift in a clade of tree-killing bark beetles. *Ecological Entomology*, *45*(2), 190–201. <https://doi.org/10.1111/een.12786>
- Six, D. L., & Biedermann, P. H. W. (2023). Fidelity or love the one you're with? Biotic complexity and tradeoffs can drive strategy and specificity in beetle-fungus by-product mutualisms. *Ecology and Evolution*, *13*(7). <https://doi.org/10.1002/ece3.10345>
- Six, D. L., De Beer, W., Duong, T. A., Carroll, A. L., & Wingfield, M. J. (2011). Fungal associates of the lodgepole pine beetle, *Dendroctonus murrayanae*. *Antonie van Leeuwenhoek, International Journal of General and Molecular Microbiology*, *100*(2), 231–244. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10482-011-9582-1>
- Six, D. L., & Klepzig, K. D. (2021). Context Dependency in Bark Beetle-Fungus Mutualisms Revisited: Assessing Potential Shifts in Interaction Outcomes Against Varied Genetic, Ecological, and Evolutionary Backgrounds. *Frontiers in Microbiology*, *12*(May). <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2021.682187>
- Six, D. L., & Wingfield, M. J. (2011). The role of phytopathogenicity in bark beetle-fungus symbioses: A challenge to the classic paradigm. *Annual Review of Entomology*, *56*(January 2011), 255–272. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-ento-120709-144839>

- Skelton, J., Johnson, A. J., Jusino, M. A., Bateman, C. C., Li, Y., & Hulcr, J. (2019). A selective fungal transport organ (mycangium) maintains coarse phylogenetic congruence between fungus-farming ambrosia beetles and their symbionts. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 286(1894). <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2018.2127>
- Strzałka, B., Kolařík, M., & Jankowiak, R. (2021). Geosmithia associated with hardwood-infesting bark and ambrosia beetles, with the description of three new species from Poland. *Antonie van Leeuwenhoek, International Journal of General and Molecular Microbiology*, 114(2), 169–194. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10482-020-01510-6>
- Sulochana, M. B., Jayachandra, S. Y., Kumar, S. K. A., & Dayanand, A. (2014). Antifungal attributes of siderophore produced by the Pseudomonas aeruginosa JAS-25. *Journal of Basic Microbiology*, 54(5), 418–424. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jobm.201200770>
- Thorpe, W. H. (1953). Cooperation among Animals. In *Nature* (Vol. 171, Issue 4350). <https://doi.org/10.1038/171453c0>
- Ummah, M. S., Arntzen, M., Bengtsson, O., Várnai, A., Delogu, F., Mathiesen, G., Eijsink, V. G. H., Moran, N. A., Degnan, P. H., Santos, S. R., Dunbar, H. E., Ochman, H., McCutcheon, J. P., Moran, N. A., Hulcr, J. J., Stelinski, L. L., Russell, S. L., Klepzig, K. D., Six, D. L., ... Moran, N. A. (2020). Symbiosis as an adaptive process and source of phenotypic complexity. *Frontiers in Microbiology*, 5(1), 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.17226/11790>
- Veselská, T., Švec, K., Kostovčík, M., Peral-Aranega, E., Garcia-Fraile, P., Křížková, B., Havlíček, V., Saati-Santamaría, E., & Kolařík, M. (2023). Proportions of taxa belonging to the gut core microbiome change throughout the life cycle and season of the bark beetle Ips typographus. *FEMS Microbiology Ecology*, 99(8), 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1093/femsec/fiad072>
- Vidal, M. C., Anneberg, T. J., Curé, A. E., Althoff, D. M., & Segraves, K. A. (2021). The variable effects of global change on insect mutualisms. *Current Opinion in Insect Science*, 47, 46–52. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cois.2021.03.002>
- Wang, D. Y. C., Kumar, S., & Hedges, S. B. (1999). Divergence time estimates for the early history of animal phyla and the origin of plants, animals and fungi. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 266(1415), 163–171. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.1999.0617>
- Williams, G. M., & Ginzal, M. D. (2021). Competitive Advantage of Geosmithia morbida in Low-Moisture Wood May Explain Historical Outbreaks of Thousand Cankers Disease and Predict the Future Fate of Juglans nigra Within Its Native Range. *Frontiers in Forests and Global Change*, 4(September), 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.3389/ffgc.2021.725066>
- Wilson, M. K., Abergel, R. J., Raymond, K. N., Arceneaux, J. E. L., & Byers, B. R. (2006). Siderophores of Bacillus anthracis, Bacillus cereus, and Bacillus thuringiensis. *Biochemical and Biophysical Research Communications*, 348(1), 320–325. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bbrc.2006.07.055>
- Wood, S. L., & Bright, D. E. (1992). Hosts of Scolytidae and Platypodidae. *Great Basin Naturalist Memoirs*, 13, 12. <https://scholarsarchive.byu.edu/gbnmAvailableat:https://scholarsarchive.byu.edu/gbnm/vol13/iss1/12>

- Yang, Y., & Luo, Y. (2011). Carbon:nitrogen stoichiometry in forest ecosystems during stand development. *Global Ecology and Biogeography*, 20(2), 354–361. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1466-8238.2010.00602.x>
- Yu, X., Ai, C., Xin, L., & Zhou, G. (2011). The siderophore-producing bacterium, *Bacillus subtilis* CAS15, has a biocontrol effect on Fusarium wilt and promotes the growth of pepper. *European Journal of Soil Biology*, 47(2), 138–145. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejsobi.2010.11.001>
- Zhao, T., Kandasamy, D., Krokene, P., Chen, J., Gershenson, J., & Hammerbacher, A. (2019). Fungal associates of the tree-killing bark beetle, *Ips typographus*, vary in virulence, ability to degrade conifer phenolics and influence bark beetle tunneling behavior. *Fungal Ecology*, 38(September), 71–79. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.funeco.2018.06.003>
- Zhou, F., Lou, Q., Wang, B., Xu, L., Cheng, C., Lu, M., & Sun, J. (2016). Altered Carbohydrates Allocation by Associated Bacteria-fungi Interactions in a Bark Beetle-microbe Symbiosis. *Scientific Reports*, 6(December 2015), 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep20135>